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**THE DIGITAL WELFARE STATE IN COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVE:
THE CASES OF KENYA AND INDIA**

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Abstract: The digital welfare state and its legal challenges. This study examines the current role of technology in welfare States and approaches being taken by legislative bodies in this regard to manage sustainably, the balance between tech and human rights. Particularly, this research seeks to unravel the history and emergence of digital identification systems and their functionality within the legal ambit. This thesis will further analyse judicial decisions from the Kenyan and Indian constitutional Courts on identification systems, and the need for equilibrium in promoting good governance, efficient identification systems and safeguarding fundamental rights such as the right to privacy and security.

Introduction

Background

Globalization, digital and technological innovations such as the internet have changed the world and the speed of these advancements is rising continuously, especially in the current 21st century.

‘The welfare state is a multi-functional and heterogeneous set of political and administrative institutions, whose purpose is to manage the structures of socialization and the capitalist economy.’¹ It is further known to be a system of governance in which the governmental institutions play a vital role in securing social insurance through the promotion of the collective good of citizens, especially those less capable of maintaining or providing their basic needs.

A principle aim of the welfare state includes equal opportunities and distribution of wealth that bridges the gap between the rich and the less privileged². This intervention is most likely to differ in various countries depending on demands and the resources available; however, basic needs such as healthcare, education and housing are integral parts of every welfare state. Over the years, the management of this social security and assistance system has evolved into a more sophisticated one built on data collection, screening through different systems including machine learning in order to intervene or provide needs in a more precise way.

Most would agree that technology has indeed made our world a more comfortable place facilitating particularly the means of transport, communication, commerce, education and even governance; factors that are indispensable to every nation. It should not come as a surprise that well-known international organizations such as the United Nations include ‘(...) upgrading the technological capabilities of industrial sectors in all countries ‘in their long-term development project objectives’ (SDG Goal 9) Griggs, David³. Regional organizations such as the EU have shown interest in this field through the European Parliament's Directorate-General for Innovation and Technological Support (DG ITEC), the Council of the EU's Communication and Information Services Directorate (SMART), and the European Commission's Directorate-General for Informatics (DIGIT), that focus on bringing IT communities of the European institutions together to find what could be more efficient approaches surrounding the emergence of technology in public administration and to

¹ Offe, Claus. Contradictions of the welfare state.

² Read more on the wealth inequality: <https://poverty.umich.edu/research-projects/policy-briefs/rising-wealth-inequality-causes-consequences-and-potential-responses/>

³ Griggs, David, et al. "Policy: Sustainable development goals for people and planet."

explore how the digital future could shape the way large organizations operate. Moreover, technology has gradually become a necessity due to its salient role in almost every community. According to the Internet usage and world population statistics, almost five out of the eight billion world population are active Internet users encompassing 59% of the global population. By now, it is conspicuous that technology is a core pillar of the modern society and society without it, is unimaginable.

Most big companies and the private sector in general have adopted technological innovations and the use of biometric data in integral parts of their functions, allowing users to access some services, virtual assistance and analyse data for marketing strategies. As mentioned above, public authorities have become aware of the importance of biometric recognition, to promote public or national security, criminal investigations, the fight against crime, anti-terrorist purposes or border control. This extends to increasing the efficient allocation of resources and correct management of public services.⁴

Our world, however, is characterized by several opinions and speculations on the advancing of technology and the role it plays in society. The mere mention of artificial intelligence, machine learning and the use of robotics propels so much scepticism and doubt in the society and in their quest to know more from the brains behind these new inventions, the realisation that there is not complete assurance of the future of technology and particularly its limitations increases such apprehension. Invariably, this frame of mind is transferred to all other sectors including the system of governance, especially when it comes to the use of personal data.

Research problem, objectives and questions

In recent times, countries are making it a priority to adopt sustainable policies that go to decrease inequalities, reduce waste and protect the environment. In accordance with the UN 2030 sustainable goals, most regions in the world are making their way towards this, an example being Europe's latest green deal.⁵ For this reason, with the broadening of the concept of technology and the introduction of innovations in the welfare state and other areas of government through data analytics, artificial intelligence storage and digitalization of the public sector have become an aim

⁴ Campisi, Patrizio. Security and privacy in biometrics. Springer, 2013

⁵ Schepelmann, Philipp, et al. "A green new deal for Europe." Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy (2009)

of most countries.⁶ In reaching this goal of facilitating archiving, identification and law enforcement, some governments have embraced policies, systems and other initiatives in various fields including public services and security. Researches have also been funded over the years towards this objective. It is evident that the welfare sector, like other industries, has benefited from technological and digital innovations.

Advancement in technology has birthed sophisticated software for identification, tools that have had various advantages on our system, saving time and resources. However, this system regarding the use of sensitive data has been questioned due to the legal issues that it triggers. Biometric data is an example, that includes face recognition, iris recognition, fingerprint or voice recognition.⁷ The General Data Processing Regulation defines it as:

“personal data obtained from a specific technical treatment, relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person and which allows or confirms the univocal identification, such as the facial image or dactyloscopic data.”⁸

It is not surprising that the operation of such software in governance through the systems like the Netherland’s ‘System Risk Indication’(SyRI),⁹ the French *fichier des titres électroniques sécurisés* (*fichier TES*)¹⁰ and the Indian Aadhar System¹¹ trigger debates on a possible threat to individuals, infringing on their personal rights and an impetus for discrimination.

These projects, though initiated for different reasons (identification, to reduce leakages in benefit systems, calculate risks, eliminate fraud, increase transparency), have similar scopes and methods in collecting and storing personal data from individuals. This is usually done with the consent of the citizens but in the long term, sets other machine learning processes in motion. The government, having access to other sectors, can accumulate the information gathered overtime from these databases including health details, financial status and biometric data making it easy to trace and monitor individuals. The problem encompasses the fact that these databases are created without the

⁶ Henman, Paul. *Governing electronically: E-government and the reconfiguration of public administration, policy and power*. Springer, 2010.

⁷ Jain, Anil, Lin Hong, and Sharath Pankanti. "Biometric identification." *Communications of the ACM* 43.2 (2000): 90-98.

⁸ Art. 4, co. 1, n. 14), General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Reg. UE 679/201

⁹ Bekker, Sonja. "Fundamental Rights in Digital Welfare States: The Case of SyRI in the Netherlands." *Netherlands Yearbook of International Law* 2019. TMC Asser Press, The Hague, 2020. 289-307.

¹⁰ Foegle, Jean-Philippe. "TES file: The Council of State gives the green light to the biometric registration of 67 million French people." *The Human Rights Review. Journal of the Center for Research and Studies on Fundamental Rights* (2018).

¹¹ Barde, Snehlata. "A Multimodal Biometric System-Aadhar Card." *i-manager's Journal on Image Processing* 5.2 (2018): 1.

knowledge of the individual, thereby creating surveillance systems that infringe upon personal rights.¹² The right to privacy is one of the main fundamental human rights breached in this case.

The question is, if rights such as security and privacy can be enjoyed with such systems in place, what boundary has been set within the digital governance as a preventive measure to refrain States from exceeding their limits? And how transparent governments must be in guaranteeing general security, especially in situations where models, algorithms and methods of codifications are kept secret to reduce the possibility of cyber-attacks, system predictions or leakages? Another, important question to be answered is the repercussions of digital governance on human rights standards.

The possibility of biased automated systems should also be considered, discussing whether it is advisable to leave important decisions amongst which judicial verdicts, access to financial aids and welfare benefits to this apparatus.

These subjects are significant and should be made a priority due to the rapid changes in our world to ultimately stay updated and work more efficiently in a short period of time. Almost every sector in our world is quickly adapting to digital innovations. This year's COVID-19 crisis has demonstrated even further the relevance of the internet, substituting all physical interactions, once considered the only possibility, with digital meetings and increasing internet usage by 70% so far.¹³ As explained by Contarello, Alberta, and Mauro Sarric, 'the internet is shifting from being a helpful adjunct to a full-on necessity in some industries.'¹⁴ Therefore, the internet has come to stay and cannot be contended with, however, there must be clarifications on legal frameworks in such fields to avoid vagueness and consequently, any form of abuse, discrimination or infringement on personal rights.

This paper discusses the role of artificial intelligence and digital innovations in governance, analysing some systems and their tendencies of birthing infringements on human rights. This thesis pursues an analytical and practical approach and takes into account procedural rules, international laws, treaties, scholarly articles, journals, existing academic literature, international and domestic legal frameworks on data protection and other subjects related to the security of individuals and how their data should be used. In reaching the aforementioned, particular emphasis is given to cases and decisions by the by the India and Kenyan constitutional courts on digital identification systems

¹² Ferguson, Andrew Guthrie. *The rise of big data policing: Surveillance, race, and the future of law enforcement*. NYU Press, 2019.

¹³ Hacker, Janine, et al. "Virtually in this together—how web-conferencing systems enabled a new virtual togetherness during the COVID-19 crisis." *European Journal of Information Systems* (2020): 1-22.

¹⁴ Contarello, Alberta, and Mauro Sarrica. "ICTs, social thinking and subjective well-being—The Internet and its representations in everyday life." *Computers in human behavior* 23.2 (2007): 1016-1032.

The welfare state, like most sectors needs technology to function but not at the expense of individual rights, increasing inequalities and injustices. Justice D. Chandrachud in his judgement on the Puttaswamy v. Union of India case stated “the constitutional guarantees cannot be subject to the vicissitudes of technology.”¹⁵ Policy makers must prioritize human rights, making sure tech companies and more importantly governments, are respecting the legal frameworks provided. In addition, some laws may need to be revised and updated to suit our fast-growing technological world. The digital innovations in governance must facilitate and focus on promoting the original concept that constructs the foundational tissues of the welfare state.

¹⁵ Bhandari, Vrinda, et al. "An Analysis of Puttaswamy: The Supreme Court's Privacy Verdict." *IndraStra Global* 11 (2017): 5.

Chapter I

1.0 The historical disposition of Human rights and the nature of the welfare state.

Prior to analysing the digital welfare state, a short briefing on its structural background is imperative to recognize the grounds of prioritization of the principles and nature of the welfare state. Protecting human rights has been a primary goal of most regional and International Organizations for as long as we can remember. The concept dates back to the French ‘Déclaration des droits de l'homme et du citoyen’ (declaration of the rights of man and of the citizen)¹⁶ of 1789, the highlight of the French revolution, that gave some form of indisputable recognition to all humans. Centuries later, after other revolutions, emancipations and two world wars, the Universal declaration of human rights was emanated in 1948 by the United nations.¹⁷ This very cardinal document also translated into five hundred languages has become the common standard of the legal frameworks and requirement of all United Nations member states as well as other organizations. It recognizes the inherent dignity and inalienable rights of every human based on freedom, justice and peace. The rights represented in the thirty articles mentioned include the right to freedom as human beings, right to life, right to fair hearing, prohibition of slavery, the right to nationality and the right to privacy, family, home etc.

Studies show that the recognition of social rights, equality and the introduction of governmental policies aimed at rebuilding states, all realization of welfare state objectives, were even more emphasized or reinforced after the world wars, gradually leaving the somewhat individualistic concept of ‘laissez-faire’¹⁸ behind. Historians, economists, political scientists and the likes have analysed over the years to better define the welfare system. In his book ‘The welfare state in historical perspective’, Asa Briggs, a renowned British historian writes about the evolution of the welfare state. According to him, this system aims at guaranteeing a minimum income for everyone irrespective of the economic situation at hand, ensuring stability and security particularly in terms of social contingencies such as sicknesses and unemployment thus reducing the rate of crisis in families.¹⁹

¹⁶ Jellinek, Georg. The declaration of the rights of man and of citizens: a contribution to modern constitutional history. H. Holt, 1901.

¹⁷ Assembly, UN General. "Universal declaration of human rights." UN General Assembly 302.2 (1948).

¹⁸ Viner, Jacob. "The intellectual history of laissez faire." A social doctrine popular in the 19th century.

¹⁹ Briggs, Asa. "The welfare state in historical perspective."

The British professor Rodney Lowe, in 'the nature of a welfare state', written in the 1930s, explained, that the term welfare state was used abusively to describe the Weimer Republic that apparently burdened the state with so many social responsibilities, undermining the political and economic sectors. England also defined the welfare state as the opposite of a 'warfare' state, serving the citizens and the international community unlike totalitarian states. Lowe adds that the modern-day welfare state is generally built on this second notion under the labour government in Britain and was accepted generally by 1950.

Thus, the welfare state hasn't only evolved overtime but varies from place to place depending on different factors including the attitude the citizens towards the 'state'. This is depicted in Toikko and Rantanen's work on how the welfare state's model influences social political attitudes.²⁰ It is observed that there is a positive notion about the welfare state in the Anglo-saxon and Nordic welfare states attracting support amongst the citizens. On the other hand, there is a rather negative connection between the continental, eastern and southern welfare states, proving less satisfaction about government intervention and more focus on individual protection or growth. In this case, where the welfare model influences the attitude of citizens, it is defined more as an attitudinal perception than a social policy.

The first analysis of the welfare state through comparative studies were based on the economic level as the main factor that introduces variations in countries. Studies that followed threw more light on the working-class mobilization and economic openness. In addition, the concept that not every state expenditure can be placed under a welfare commitment emerged afterwards, bringing more clarity over time. Most sociologists and economists would agree that there are insufficient models on the theory of the welfare state, nevertheless, the few models analysed factors that have to be considered in confirming the existence of a welfare state including the structure of the state²¹, which should concentrate on solving the needs of the individuals and the paradigm of aid given. Assistance could be residual (introduced only when there is a failure to meet one's own needs) or institutional (where policies are enacted for the collective good), expanding the scope of the welfare state.

Empirical researches have been fundamental in deducing the characteristics and development of welfare states over the years treating topics such as capitalism, de-commodification and nation-

²⁰ Timo Toikko & Teemu Rantanen (2017) How does the welfare state model influence social political attitudes? An analysis of citizens' concrete and abstract attitudes toward poverty, *Journal of International and Comparative Social Policy*.

²¹ Therborn, Göran. When, how and why does a state become a welfare state? 1983.

building. Prior to these discussions, there were ongoing debates on the effect of welfare states and social citizenship on class stratification, thus the transformation of the capitalist society. This very important topic on the relationship between capitalism and the welfare state was raised by various economists, philosophers and intellectuals including the neo liberalist Adam Smith, who emphasized on promoting individual interests and the salience of the market (acquisition of property and private entities) as a solution to decrease and eventually eliminate the idea of classes in the society.²² The many that followed such as Nassau senior and John S. Mill, acknowledged that a liberal market was the required steppingstone for less government intervention and achieving a free market. Gosta Esping -Andersen, the Danish sociologist states in his book 'The three worlds of the welfare state' that this notion of a liberalised market was fuelled principally by the absolutistic regime they lived in that exhibited 'mercantilist protectionism and ubiquitous corruption.'

In considering comparative studies as evidence of various types of this regime, Esping-Andersen further explains this, categorizing it into three perspectives depending on their diverse historical and geographical background.²³ First, the liberal welfare state is characterized by a maximum free market and minimum state interference. Their conviction that democracy would usurp the market and the social order led to the conception of the conservative welfare state. This system highlights a government that has a minimum centralized system of governing where decisions are made by the local levels instead of a centralized government. Lastly, the social-democratic welfare state is when the state promotes the social and economic well-being of its citizens based on the principles of equality, distribution of wealth with the objective of diminishing social divisions and eradicating poverty. Other basis of divergence within these perspectives include the degree of decommodification, the pattern of social stratification and the relative ratio of the state to market in pension regime.

The modern welfare state programs were mostly characterized by poverty relief programs i.e. economic and humanitarian-based measures set to give the less privileged an opportunity to overcome poverty. Some programs were aimed at achieving autonomous benefit systems while others were more dependent on the help of the state. We can say that the great depression that hit the world's economy between the end of the 1020s and the beginning of the 1930s further conveyed the concept of the welfare state to various countries. This system was easily accepted as a balance

²² Smith, Adam. *The Wealth of Nations: An inquiry into the nature and causes of the Wealth of Nations.*

²³ Esping-Andersen, Gøsta. "4 the three political economies of the welfare state."

between communism and the very liberal ‘laissez- faire’ ideology. Eileen McDonagh, an American political scientist explains in her research paper on the ‘monarchical origins of the welfare state’, that a shift to the welfare state regime is easier where there was previously a monarchy playing a parental role on a familial basis (also defined as patrimonialism by Max Weber), making it easier for the state to assume position as a parental steward.²⁴ This may be another reason why some countries are more inclined to the notion of state intervention than others. Even so, the renowned British sociologist Thomas Humphrey Marshall, points out that every welfare state should merge welfare, democracy and capitalism, creating a balanced system, where citizens are entitled to social, political and civil privileges (Citizenship and Social Class- 1950).²⁵ The social rights refer to all rights related to economic welfare and stability, not leaving out the right to enjoy social heritage with the help of the educational and social institutions. The political rights include the right to participate in the election of representatives to govern the people. Lastly, civil rights cover the individual freedom i.e. the Right to liberty, Freedom of speech, the Right to own property, Right to Justice and the likes. This is where we stand today, even on the global level, nations through International Organizations are working to achieve this equilibrium.

1.1 The Welfare state and technology.

The use of technology is one of the main factors that have greatly influenced the welfare state in recent times. Towards the end of the 20th century, in post-world war II era, industrialization accelerated incredibly in various sectors introducing even more faster systems to increase production and manage time effectively. The concept of the internet, where data is broken down into smaller pieces and can be transferred easily to another destination known as the ‘Transmission control protocol or Internet protocol’ which emerged in 1974 by the computer scientist Vinton Cerf and electrical engineer Robert Kahn. By 2017, systems such as these would be developed to analyse data, learn to memorize and even predict behaviours. Today, there are barely any sectors that function without the use of technology in data storage, marketing, law enforcement, identification and the likes. It should not come as a surprise that welfare states have adopted this system over the years mostly to acquire more information in less time and to facilitate the role of the public administration. In addition, most countries are beginning to integrate the concept of sustainability

²⁴ McDonagh, Eileen. "Ripples from the First Wave: The Monarchical Origins of the Welfare State."

²⁵ Marshall, Thomas Humphrey. Citizenship and social class.

which also promotes the digitalization and sometimes the centralization of information into databases with the objective of reducing waste (aside facilitate accessibility to information).

The term e-governance describes the use of information and communication technology in the activities and services of the government and its agencies. Literally speaking, we can say that the world is currently governed by technology. The multi-disciplinary nature of this topic has attracted people from diverse fields to its study. In 1986, Christopher Hood, a Professor at the Oxford University and social scientist published 'The Tools of the Government', a book that analyses the toolkit of the government, especially in gathering information and organizing the state. It goes on to analyse the possible effectors and detectors of the government; the first category is used in implementing tasks and objectives whereas the detectors are used in extracting information. The increase in awareness of digital states continues with other studies such as that of Perri 6, a British social scientist who wrote 'E -Governance, Styles of political judgement in the information Age polity'²⁶, a book in which he also states the characteristics of e-government namely e-service management, e-democracy and e-governance.

Sociologists, tech scholars, political scientists and other researchers have worked on studying how rapid our world is changing due to technological innovations and the effects on society. This study is also known as technological literature, familiarizing with the 'seamless web' created by socio-technical systems. In the next chapter, we will dive more into this world of technology and how complex and simultaneously fragile our systems are becoming, especially in terms of data. However, one main system under data collection that was, and still is subject of debate and criticism, is identification.

As stated previously, technology has been introduced into identification systems facilitating the access to data. Biometric data is one of the main innovative instruments being used by most states to protect national security, for investigations and to increase the efficient allocation of resources amongst others. However, the data is mostly stored in a repository, which could render data vulnerable to data breach and attacks.²⁷

Another issue worth debating about is the automated decision-making systems built with biometric data. It is seen as a substitution of human capabilities, where there is a commodification of human behaviour. Interestingly, one of the predispositions addressed during the 20th century debates

²⁶ Perri, P. e-Governance: Styles of political judgment in the information age polity.

²⁷ Formici, Giulia. "Sistemi di riconoscimento e dati biometrici: una nuova sfida per i Legislatori e le Corti."

concerning the socio-technical relations, is the concept of agency. Humans have agency, which is the consciousness to determine behaviour and this ability cannot be attributed to technological artefacts. Others explained that non-humans were to be actors and not conscious beings, independent from human actions and contributing to different sectors.²⁸

In addition, the ‘neutrality’ of these technological artefacts was questioned, weighing their detachment from moral and politically based concepts. These instruments may have nothing to do with these areas but would automatically assume the moral and political values of their users. Decades afterwards, a current discussion particularly referring to Artificial Intelligence is the kind of information being fed to the systems. The idea of systems that give biased outcomes based on distorted information depends on the values, mindset and stands of their programmers.

It is important to know that there is a research aimed at defining the exact role of technology and its limits when it comes to rather intricate tasks that need actual 'human cognitive abilities'. However, technology is constantly evolving and gaining what Henman calls ‘a productive form of power’ in various fields and bringing innovation to them; reason for which there is a need for strategic attention in this field.

1.2. A legal Approach to the digital welfare state.

So far, there have been more researches on the sociological approach to the digital welfare state in comparison to a legal approach. This may be due to the overwhelming changes, brought by digital innovations, that society has had to assimilate in very little time. A report of the United Nations by Philip Alston, the United Nations special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights, warned that humankind must ‘alter course significantly and rapidly, to avoid stumbling zombie-like into a digital-welfare dystopia.’²⁹ Furthermore, it added that ‘the digital transformation may need to be guided by the respect for human rights and grounded in hard law.’

The need for a legal framework became necessary particularly when technology was given some power over important tasks such as automated decision- making, investigations and identification. We can say that since the legal aspect of the digital welfare state relied mostly on the evolvement of

²⁸ Callon, Michel, Arie Rip, and John Law, eds. Mapping the dynamics of science and technology: Sociology of science in the real world.

²⁹ Report of the UN Special Rapporteur on the Digital Welfare state (<https://www.ohchr.org/EN/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=25156>)

technology, the accelerated change in this sector over a short period of time, created a gap until recent times. The General Data Processing Regulation (GDPR)³⁰, a main reference for Data protection laws, was enacted in 2018 under the European privacy framework. In a research article written by Michelle Goddard,³¹ addressing the actual development of the digital welfare state in Europe, we understand that the intention is for it to have a global impact due to the salience of privacy as a fundamental right.

We must take into consideration the fact that various countries have enacted data protection laws, although some have more advanced and detailed legislation than others. Results from research carried out by DLA Piper, a global law firm show the level of data protection and their enforcement in countries around the world, placing them in four categories: limited, moderate, robust and heavy. The states with limited data protection and implementation include Zambia, Iran, Kenya, India whereas Australia, Canada, the United States of America and most countries in Europe have an effective implementation of structured data protection laws.

Until recently, there has been a continuous curiosity to discover the effects of technology in governance and subsequently on the society. Very little intervention on the legal-empirical work of the digital welfare state has been covered. There is an evident gap in the legal framework of this phenomenon, leaving uncertainties in relation to technology as a monopoly on its own and how data is handled by governments. This deficit, though being gradually bridged with time, still needs to be accelerated, through additional legislation, to match the ongoing digital transformation.

1.3 Methodology

This study shall focus on the digital welfare state using a more qualitative approach. With the use of reports and other researches, we will explore the prevalence of technology in our modern world and the role it plays in our welfare states.

This analysis will be obtained through a study on the characteristics of a welfare state and the egression of the digital welfare state. To comprehend the matter further, the next chapters will be channelled to technology and Artificial Intelligence, their functions, their current limits, their role as

³⁰ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance), [2016] OJ L 119/1

³¹ Goddard, Michelle. "The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): European Regulation That Has a Global Impact."

tools of the government and the effects they may convey on our society, particularly the most vulnerable (social rights). Furthermore, it is salient to assimilate the lawfulness of this phenomenon studying the effectiveness of existing national and international laws related to the topics mentioned above. This is to ease us into understanding if the rights of citizens are protected, how prepared states are for such robust systems and if there is any cause for alarm and uncertainty.

In this work, we aim is also to understand how best the utilization of this governmental instrument, that has a high probability of towering in the near future, could be managed sustainably, especially by the law. Prior to this, with the help of case laws and the adjudication of the Supreme Courts of Kenya and India, we will discuss from a comparative perspective the subject of artificial intelligence and identification as governmental instruments and the issues that emerge, especially with regards to social rights.

To conclude, the topic of a sustainable digital welfare state will be discussed to answer some questions and pinpointing possible solutions to curb infringements on individual rights and promote the collective good.

Chapter II

2.0 Defining the Welfare State

To begin with, the concept of 'welfare' can be defined as a general state of health or degree of success of a person, business or even country. It can also be referred to as a statutory procedure or social effort designed to promote the basic physical and material growth. Welfare is an overall state of well-being. Keeping this in mind, the industrialization, especially at the end of the nineteenth century, followed by the world wars, the great depression all resulting in an increase in social solidarity, are events that caused an expansion of the welfare state.

A rather ambiguous but standard definition of a welfare state is a system in which the government of a country provides social services such as healthcare, housing, unemployment benefit, etc. to people who need them. In other words, the nation takes charge for the economic and social wellbeing of its citizens based on principles such as equal opportunities, the distribution of wealth and public responsibility for those who are not in the position to shoulder their basic needs using various tools. In other terms, the state protects its own from the negative effects of living in capitalist economies. The early welfare systems were instituted through public pensions and social insurance and additionally, the modern welfare states employ tools such as taxes and contributions. The combination of these tools and the cooperation between the state, market and family also contribute qualitatively to welfare-state regimes, allowing us to differentiate between one type of welfare state and the other. According to Esping- Andersen, a Danish political sociologist, 'the welfare-state can be sub sectioned into three 'cluster-regimes', liberal, conservative and social-democratic.'³²

The liberalists sustain that the economy and wellbeing of the citizens would thrive better where the state intervention is minimum with fairly modest social insurance programs (and benefits), directed mainly to low-income workers and state dependents. This reduces the possibility of monopolies, inequalities and inefficiencies. In this system, a platform is created to give possibility to more competition on the market passively, by offering minimum guarantee or actively, through incentivizing private welfare schemes thus allowing people of lower classes to rise in society.

Then, the democratic system emerged, opening the market further to all classes and to levelling social hierarchical structures. In response to this was the opposition of the conservatives that

³² Esping-Andersen, Gøsta. "4 the three political economies of the welfare state." Part I – The three welfare state regimes

prioritize social rights over market efficiency and commodification. This feature was accompanied by what Esping called ‘the preservation of status differentials’, that associated rights to one’s level in society. Other features that shaped the conservative welfare state were the power to redistribute wealth, the attachment to traditional family values and the marginalization of the role of some actors, for example, private insurance companies. Where the family is concerned, the principle of subsidiarity may apply. This conveys power to the state only when the family has exhausted its ability to sustain itself. Even so, this system favoured the monarchical welfare states for their believe in a more authoritarian system based on discipline and traditional values, that would still address welfare, the market and class harmony. Nations characterized with this system include France, Germany and Italy.

Lastly, the social democratic welfare-state, characterized by a smaller ‘regime-cluster’, was developed during the social reform era. This system is based on the principles of universalism, equality and the de-commodification of social rights. In addition, the concept of stratification and division of the societal tissue is minimum, and a high level of equality is fostered. The middle-class workers are entitled to upgraded benefits, social services and rights. Welfare initiatives in the social-democratic systems are incorporated under one universal insurance program to make policies addressing the market as well as the traditional family. As opposed to the conservative welfare state and similarly to the liberalist system, this system supports the family, focusing on the individual wellbeing of its citizens. It aims to de-commodify welfare services, undoing what the market-based approach established, erecting an undivided structure. This increases the level of responsibility and social burden the state assumes, supporting children, the aged and the less privileged and addressing issues such as unemployment. A downside to this system is how, in shouldering its rather heavy task, the social-democratic welfare state minimizes social obstacles and focuses on increasing revenue, mostly through maintaining a limited number of people living on welfare benefits, leaving the majority in the working class.

It is worth noting that there are no pure cases of liberal, conservative or social-democratic welfare states. Most countries have infused systems with different arrangements of these features depending on their political, social and even historical backgrounds. T.K. Marshall, a British sociologist, described the modern welfare state as ‘a combination of democracy, welfare and capitalism³³.’ It is through the birth of this modern welfare state that civil, political and social rights emerge from the

³³ Marshall, Thomas Humphrey, and Thomas Burton Bottomore. *Citizenship and social class*. Vol. 2.

end of the eighteenth century. Civil rights are absolute and were established before the others. They are directed to secure the integrity of citizens, preventing discriminations based on gender, race, ethnicity, etc. Examples are the right to speech, the right to privacy, the right to vote and the right to fair trial.³⁴ However, social rights are more dependent on the society or nations economic development. They include the right to security, shelter and an adequate standard of living.

Social rights form part of the fundamental human rights and the objective of every welfare state is to promote such rights within its society. Currently, countries with welfare state regimes include Germany, Norway, Greece, Italy, Denmark, India, France, The Netherlands, Japan amongst others; evidence, that the concept is widespread across various countries. Albeit, every system may differ in structure as mentioned above.

Focusing on the dynamic characteristics and evolution of the welfare state, aside possible divergence of the systems, methods and instruments of governance are subject to improvements and remodelling. Concrete examples can be found in the technological developments burgeoning in recent times which have played principal roles in advancing our systems and should be taken seriously, especially by the Law.

2.1. The Digital Welfare State and it's attributes or tools

It is unfeasible to compare our world to what it was a century ago. So much has taken place and technology has been integral and a catalyst in this change. Picking up from where we left off in the previous paragraph, the digital structural change in recent years have penetrated almost every sector including public administration, health and governance; a rather unexpected and inevitable occurrence.

Starting off on the note that digitalization is the usage of technology to produce or deliver a product or service, we can say a digital approach to governance has become a necessity especially in order to increase productivity, adapt to modern systems and cut costs. In performing its tasks, the welfare state for the lasts decades have adapted new methods of protecting rights, implementing and enforcing laws, making policies aimed to promote equality and welfare support.³⁵ You would say

³⁴ <https://www.frontlinedefenders.org/en/right/civil-political-rights>

³⁵ Rachinger, Michael, et al. "Digitalization and its influence on business model innovation." *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management* (2019).

that that this would be an engaging and almost impossible task however digitalizing entire systems has proved to be possible even at a frightening speed. This period is termed as the era of digital governance, where developed countries are diving into advanced systems such as algorithm based predictive policies, voting electronically, digitalization of justice and programs related to immigration, facial recognition applications; whereas developing countries, even though slightly behind, are initiating national and international digital-based systems such as the biometric identification.³⁶

The aim of the ‘digital welfare state’ emerging all over is to transfer most of the information correlated to the population to centralized data systems through improved welfare programs and enhanced financial and security systems. These systems include other administrative, healthcare and social welfare services that are provided to the citizens. In fact, social protection and assistance programs are increasingly becoming automated with the help of advanced technologies and Artificial Intelligence, mandated to predict, automate, monitor, identify, detect and sometimes punish. This rather costly yet imperative transformation is an impetus of structural and societal change.

It is important to understand the pivotal role of technology in today’s welfare state since it has become an intricate part of our societal anatomy and daily lives. Apart from the biometric passports being introduced into our systems, we can think of various innovative initiatives adopted by our governments. Such instruments include automated medicine inventory management system, that promotes transparency, minimizes theft and improves medicine availability³⁷ ; the digital clocking systems, used in various working places including the public sectors, hotels, commercial centres and the likes ; public sector recruitment, performance review and monitoring that reduces any signs of nepotism and increases efficiency; machine learning programs that solve emerging issues being saved in a shorter period of time compared to the human method of analysis³⁸.

In 2016 the World Economic Forum estimated a ‘crucial change’ in the healthcare sector particularly a shift towards a more ‘customer-centric’, where the focus is on patient empowerment, self -management and harnesses the participation of citizens in taking more responsibility for their

³⁶ Gregson, Jon, et al. The future of knowledge sharing in a digital age: Exploring impacts and policy implications for development. No. IDS Evidence Report; 125. IDS, 2015.

³⁷ DFID (2018) Project Completion Review. DFID Pakistan: Sub-National Governance Programme (SNG)

³⁸ Paul, A. Jolley, C. & Anthony, A. (2018) Reflecting the Past, Shaping the Future: Making AI Work for International Development. USAID.

health³⁹. Van Niekerk, et al., observed that, automation in the health sector covers various tasks such as facilitating the access to healthcare professionals in order to increase the knowledge on health information, promote patient engagement initiatives, post-hospital and satisfaction surveys⁴⁰. A Ugandan initiative launched by the Medical Concierge Group (TMCG) was birth purposely for this, like most digitalized programs, aim to increase access to information on healthcare especially in poor communities and maximize the resources of the state's healthcare facilities.

The judiciary also counts as one of the pillars subject to digital transformation and notion of 'digital justice' abandons the old paper-based procedures and redefines the delivery of justice, thriving to reach fairer, cost-effective and efficient results. Digital justice tackles some challenges in the field such as limited resources, that result in a backlog of cases and long-lasting court procedures; unsustainable use of paper (the UK recorded a total usage of 1 million paper a day making 365 million a year), that could affect the efficiency of the administration of justice in cases of file misplacements, lack of quality transportation etc. An important factor that should be considered is that digital justice reduces the chances of corruption through the modification or pilfering of documents/dockets, hence, promoting transparency. Other advantages of this system are the possibility of scheduling electronically, remote working to collaborate more efficiently, automated archiving, physical and cyber court security, online portals that give citizens the opportunity to interact with the law and even virtual courts where necessary.⁴¹ An example is the Azerbaijani approach to reducing civil court Backlogs mainly concentrated on very straightforward cases such as claims for unpaid bills, a project that the world bank defines as a 'key innovation.'⁴² Through its partnership with the private sector, an automated system was created to take charge of all uncontested cases; this way, judges have more time to address and prioritize other cases, depending on their measure of sensitivity and importance.

According to a research article written in collaboration with the deutsche bank in 2019 regarding the digital change in relation to welfare states, the widespread of digitalization in all sectors has the potential to increase productivity⁴³ and subsequently, economic growth. In fact, studies show that

³⁹ World-Economic-Forum. World Economic Forum White Paper. Digital Transformation of Industries: In collaboration with Accenture, 2016.

⁴⁰ Van Niekerk, L., et al. "Social innovation in health: case studies and lessons learned from low-and middle-income countries." (2017).

⁴¹ Donoghue, Jane. "The rise of digital justice: courtroom technology, public participation and access to justice." *The Modern Law Review* 80.6 (2017): 995-1025.

⁴² World Bank (2018) Improving public sector performance through innovation and inter-agency coordination.

⁴³ Becker, Sebastian, Stefan Schneider, and Deutsche Bank AG. "Digital structural change and the welfare state in the 21st century."

the digitalizing of systems result in higher income and prosperity for the country within a shorter period and with a smaller workforce that earns higher wages. This is what ‘digitalization optimists’ term as an inclusive growth that curbs demographic burdens and expands the welfare state.

In opposition to this, other researchers express some form of uncertainties regarding the labour market of the welfare state. A smaller workforce with increased wage may interpret as an increase in inequalities related to income, the distribution of wealth and other social related factors and even policies. The probability that automation may worsen the gap between ‘high-qualified high-earners’ and ‘low-qualified low-earners’ burdens the employment opportunities further. This is likely to manifest in most industrialized countries particularly those with higher possibilities of automation. In 2015 the chief economist of the Bank of England gave a speech⁴⁴ and mentioned how the ‘third age of the machine’ could undermine the labour market and cause an income imbalance. We will analyse similar circumstances on more influential levels subsequently.

2.2. Artificial Intelligence as a tool in Digital Welfare

To understand the motives behind the uncertainties regarding the digital welfare state and the role of advanced technology, specifically Artificial Intelligence in governance, we need to examine briefly its definition, how it works, advantages and eventual disadvantages or limitations in relation to our interest in the digital welfare state. This way, before reaching the legal framework of this research, we grasp the depth and complexity of the topic being dealt with in our countries, from a holistic viewpoint.

According to the Statistical analysis team (SAS), a consortium of statistical analysis, the term artificial intelligence was coined at Dartmouth College, Hannover in 1956 by John McCarthy, a renowned computer scientist. The years that followed that period were characterized by research and the establishment of expertise teams with the goal of creating systems that could solve problems efficiently and systems that could learn by themselves.⁴⁵

Calculating, perception analogies, learning from experience, storing & retrieving information from memory, problem-solving, classification and adapting to new situations are the abilities of an

⁴⁴ Haldane, Andy. "Labour's share." Speech at the Trades Union Congress, London.

⁴⁵ Aidukas, Arnas. Data Privacy and Artificial Intelligence: Is General Data Protection Regulation the Right Regulation in the Age of Intelligent Machines?. Diss. Mykolo Romerio universitetas, 2018.

Intelligent System or Intelligent Machines. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a broad sector of computer science that puts machines in a position to assume behaviours derived from human intelligence.⁴⁶ Previously, the idea of substituting very underlying factors of production that form the input such as labour and capital was unimaginable mainly because machines were not yet capable of replacing significant tasks that formed the work process. Nonetheless, we can say that technology and all it has to offer has reversed this assumption. These elements that can automate cognitive routine jobs and other tasks, forming this new era, include ‘deep learning’, ‘big data’ and AI.⁴⁷

Artificial Intelligence, when analysed from a more technical perspective, is a rather broad concept that can be sub-sectioned into two categories. The first is Artificial Narrow Intelligence that focuses on one activity or domain at a time such as a self-driving car or AI specialised in chess. The second is Artificial General Intelligence (strong AI), that is taught to carry out various tasks, just like human beings.⁴⁸ Between these two, the first is advanced and evident in our livelihood due to its straightforward requirements, patterns, rules, pre-determined right answers, and semi-formal or formal structures that make up the process⁴⁹; whereas computer analysts say that artificial general intelligence still has a long way to go.

Artificial intelligence depends on various tools to function. Machine learning, also known as supervised learning, is one of the main tools of AI and is very common in its systems. It gives software the ability to learn. In achieving high performance with this modern instrument, the necessary requisites include Big Data⁵⁰, that facilitates the analysis and extraction of information from huge data sets; and the training of high neural networks capable of processing data and retrieving more accurate results similar to the human brain. This innovation studies patterns and preferences overtime and gives systems the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed constantly by the user. An important characteristic of automated systems are these databases

⁴⁶ Ganji, Divya S., and Sharayu Karandikar. "Artificial Intelligence: A Risk Factor."

⁴⁷ Deep learning is a part of machine learning system that trains a computer to perform human-like tasks, such as recognizing speech, identifying images or making predictions. Big data is the huge amount of data collected that contains greater variety and arrives in increasing volumes with high velocity. In fact, 90% of the world's data was generated in the past two years and now computers make sense of this more quickly. For more information on deep learning, big data and AI see:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mJeNghZXtMo&feature=youtu.be> ; Also look at: Andrejevic, Mark. "The Big Data Divide." International Journal of Communication 8, no 17 (2014): 1673-1689.

⁴⁸ Ganji, Divya S., and Sharayu Karandikar. "Artificial Intelligence: A Risk Factor." Par 1-3

⁴⁹ Vincent, James. "Open AI's new multitasking AI writes, translates, and slanders." The Verge. The Verge, February 14 (2019). See James Vincent, The State of AI in 2019, VERGE (Jan. 28, 2019, 8:00 AM),

<https://www.theverge.com/2019/1/28/18197520/ai-artificial-intelligence-machine-learning> computational-science [https://perma.cc/9JAB-8YLQ].

⁵⁰ To read more on big data see: <https://www.oracle.com/big-data/what-is-big-data.html>

created. A good number of information or data is collected (Big Data) according to what is required and grouped into data sets. Through these sets, the automated systems are taught to recognize objects, elements or pictures and match them to an identity. Considering an image and identity, the neural networks read the pixels, detect a recognition and give a corresponding data which the learning system memorizes. For example, the software created for smart speakers go through similar learning processes such as word detection, speech recognition and intent recognition. Ultimately, these systems get more intelligent and are able to recognize subjects more quickly. This machine learning system's mappings can be applied to various sectors, we can talk of the transport sector (self-driven cars), security for example the identity verification systems, the marketing sector, sales, automated systems in finance, recruiting, public administration and even agriculture.

A relevant field to us is the identity verification, made a target of the 2030 Sustainable goals (target 16.9), to assign to every individual a legal identity also through birth registration. The world bank's identification for development campaign (ID4D), was launched to support the use of digital technologies in identity documents to facilitate access to benefits and other entitlements as citizens. India's Aadhaar system⁵¹ and the Italian digital public Identity System (SPID)⁵² are few examples of digital identification systems. These systems collect detailed data such as hand geometry, fingerprints, retina and iris patterns, voice waves; which are stored and processed through biometric matching types. These include the 'one-to-one' (1:1) and the one-to-many (1: N) verifications with which the captured biometric template is compared to one pre-stored in a database or all the stored biometric templates in the system.⁵³ According to experts, the one-to-many is the best way to prevent duplicates, identity theft and fraud at service points because it searches the entire biometric database, thus, assumes a higher level of security.

The application of computer science and AI in law is also be put into consideration. This process begun towards the end of the last century with knowledge representation and rule-based legal systems. The International conference of Artificial Intelligence and Law (ICAAIL) was introduced then to showcase and discuss the applications of AI in law.⁵⁴ Today, the International Association of Artificial Intelligence still focuses on executable models of legislation, formal models of legal

⁵¹ The Indian Identification system, also the world's largest identification system, is characterized by 12-digit unique identity number targeted for the Delivery of Financial and other Subsidies, benefits and services (Aadhaar Act, 2016)

⁵² SPID is the Public Digital Identity System that guarantees all citizens and businesses a unique, safe and secure access to the digital services of the Public Administration and private adhering entities through a username and password.

⁵³ Joe Kubilius. Understanding the digital world

⁵⁴ ICAAIL 2015—First Call for Papers, Int'l Ass'n For Artificial Intelligence (Sept. 10, 2014, 8:53 AM)

reasoning, computational models of argumentation and decision making, automated information extraction from legal databases and texts.

Regarding the future of AI, projects on artificial general intelligence (AGI) are still in the developing state and are constantly in a state of flux. Defining certain terms in this industry is still fluid and constantly evolving. Whereas normal AI systems are programmed by humans to automate tasks carried out by humans, AGI expects machines to be as smart and intelligent as humans, performing the same intellectual tasks successfully. Smith, Aaron, and Janna Anderson explained that we may be a decade away from living in a world with robotic servers' as depicted in some movies.⁵⁵ This is to illustrate the depth of impact that is being created and how far it could go in the future. The welfare state's databases designed to simplify tasks, spot emerging problems more quickly, store information in order to facilitate their access and promote transparency; though helpful, must be understood thoroughly, especially by the law in order to approach it effectively.

In relation to this, it is equally important to express the challenges of Artificial intelligence and machine learning systems. Even though AI is thriving statistically speaking and ML systems are making enough good decisions to increase efficiency, it may not be doing as well with individual decision-making or cases. There is a probability that suboptimal decisions may be deduced in the process. Experts say this may be a consequence of the huge amount of data required in ML as opposed to the human ability to grasp information from small data sets. Subsequently, 'many ML and AI systems may provide wrong or inappropriate answers if used in a context different from their training environment' (Paul, et. al., 2018).⁵⁶ This creates an opaque vision of the source of some decisions, which may not explicitly have been taken by developers. This does not only apply to those affected by it, but those using it and even those who created them.

Another challenge of automated systems is the possibility of building biased systems. The machine learning construction procedure, as stated above, requires that data is fed to the system to teach recognition and identification. The system may assume, in a high or low ratio, the choices, skills, perceptions and biases of their developers during the different stages of automation. Such machine learning systems are not just technological and mechanical but have a social impact. We can also describe this as a socio-technical system, where 'technologies shape, and are shaped by people,

⁵⁵ Smith, Aaron, and Janna Anderson. "AI, Robotics, and the Future of Jobs." Pew Research Center 6 (2014): 51.

⁵⁶ Paul, A. Jolley, C. & Anthony, A. (2018) Reflecting the Past, Shaping the Future: Making AI Work for International Development. USAID.

organizations and policies.⁵⁷ This should not be taken lightly since it may easily result inadvertently in various forms of unfairness and discrimination related to gender biases, beliefs, racial origin, ethnicity, etc.⁵⁸ Developed countries have discovered that ML systems ‘have sometimes been found to automate racial profiling, to foster surveillance, and to perpetuate racial stereotypes. Algorithms may be used, either intentionally or unintentionally, in ways that result in disparate or unfair outcomes between minority and majority populations’ (Paul, et al., 2018). These flaws may be evident in different contexts depending on states’ historical backgrounds and must be addressed appropriately since automated systems are not as neutral as they seem.⁵⁹

Another limitation of AI is the possibility of adversarial attacks i.e. when the system is faulted or ‘fooled’. These are advanced techniques to subvert otherwise reliable machine-learning systems. We are talking of imperceptible changes difficult to trace, whereby the system’s assigned task is diverted. Similar attacks are recorded regarding important databases, in charge of high-profile information on security, healthcare and other sectors. Reasons behind these attacks may vary. For example, healthcare sectors being characterized by competing interests with billions of dollars at stake in systems’ outputs.⁶⁰ This raises concerns about the implementation of deep learning systems especially in the government or public administration.

The quality of data used by machine learning can impact positively or negatively the functionality of the model. This can be a challenge to artificial intelligence due difficulties in gathering good data. In a book written on ‘Making AI Work for International Development’, it is stated that data ‘proxies are imperfect stand-ins for the values we want to measure, and they can introduce distortions’ (Paul, et al., 2018). This requires more attention directed to ‘strengthening local technical capacity; strengthening relevant governance structures; ensuring responsible data practices; ensuring responsible shared learning; bringing diverse perspectives into model building; designing to facilitate model interpretability’ (Paul et. al. 2018, p. 74-79). In relation to this, the

⁵⁷ Bilal, Muhammad, et al. "Big Data in the construction industry: A review of present status, opportunities, and future trends." *Advanced engineering informatics* 30.3 (2016): 500-521.

⁵⁸ Issues also raised by Dr Tinmit Gebru (research scientist who worked previously in the ethical AI team at google)

⁵⁹ Eubanks, V. (2018). *Automating inequality: How high-tech tools profile, police, and punish the poor*. St. Martin's Press. Eubanks, with the help of real experiences lived by others, makes evident that ‘key drivers in the designing of these algorithmic decision-making aids’ are in fact traditional prejudices and stereotypes of the recipients of some form of assistance or benefit. Ex: the Allegheny Family Screening Tool that considered data extracted from past events of relatives of the subject (during their childhood) prior to predicting which children may need the intervention of social services agencies. Thus, ‘punishing contemporary families for circumstances experienced intergenerationally’ (par 152). Eubanks further pointed out the existence of racially biased data in the system, particularly towards African American and working class individuals (par 153).

⁶⁰ <https://science.sciencemag.org/content/363/6433/1287>

lack of effective ICT infrastructures may also pose as a difficulty for AI systems. Other possible challenges include misaligning AI generated information with traditional information and decision-making methods; privacy concerns related to data gathering and data protection; unclear elements of automation and its outcome etc.

Digitalization is now a well-known term under which profound changes of the labour market can be summarized. Currently, our welfare state uses these tools and more in various sectors, however these platforms are constantly evolving and prone to becoming more complex in the future. Automation, i.e. the increasing use of robots, "intelligent" machines and more comprehensive algorithms that are no longer restricted to routine tasks, may pose as 'digital threats' to the welfare state. In November 2017, Robert Stephen, Professor of machine-learning at the Oxford University, in an interview with Aljazeera mentioned, that experts in his field had been constantly working on bettering machine learning systems to achieve global societal benefits. These systems, however, would have the tendency of assuming more 'human-like abilities in such a wide range of areas that they will begin to replace human beings. Also, he added that humans are partly in control of the situation and there is much legislature, compliance and policy to wrap our heads round. This hint of uncertainty towards this topic throws even more light on the complexity of this subject and heightens the notion of the sceptical future of the welfare state.

2.3. The paradox of the Digital Welfare State

It is obvious that a major concern of citizens is the future with artificial intelligence-based systems and robotic systems. However, there are more concerning matters invisible to most of us.

Governments across the globe continue to adopt technology-centred strategies transforming public services with minimal public debate or accountability ⁶¹.

At the beginning of this research, we touched on the concept of the welfare state which sets the government in the position to play an active role in the economy, making sure markets are efficient, setting the wellbeing of its people as a priority, aiming to reach the less privileged, facilitating access to benefits, addressing social rights and entitlement rights, quality healthcare through

⁶¹ 'the digitization of welfare systems has been accompanied by deep reductions in the overall welfare budget, a narrowing of the beneficiary pool, the elimination of some services, the introduction of demanding and intrusive forms of conditionality, the pursuit of behavioural modification goals, the imposition of stronger sanctions regimes and a complete reversal of the traditional notion that the State should be accountable to the individual.' (UN Report of the Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights Par 5)

policies and rightful implementation of laws based on established principles. The welfare state overtime is said to represent the embodied response to the best approach to building a relatively cohesive economic, cultural, social and political order.⁶²

The use of automation has had an important impact on the welfare state's performance and its continuous evolution and relevance in various sectors. However, doubts have been raised, curiosities and problematic cases expressed with a need to be addressed. Observations on a few digital welfare state activities in recent times pose contradictions to the original nature of the welfare state.

Technology has been useful to systems of social protection and assistance. In most countries, the 'welfare' aim is to achieve a more inclusive relationship between citizens and the state, making them responsible of their own needs; promote good governance, higher level of wellbeing, credibility, a collaborative approach, efficient services and transparency. These digital systems entail identity verification systems, eligibility assessment, welfare benefit calculation and payments, fraud prevention and detection systems, communication between welfare authorities and beneficiaries.

The UN special rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights Philip Alston, in a report on the correlation between the digital welfare state and human rights, stated that although such advanced systems are scientific and neutral, they can reflect values and perceptions contradictory to that of human rights. Additionally, recipients of these benefits have had to endure a certain level of rigid demands, dispensable conditions and intrusive behaviour; an exploitation of their helplessness and powerlessness that infringes their right to integrity as citizens.

The political science professor and activist Virginia Eubanks, claimed in an article that such systems of the government have 'imposed on beneficiaries a new regime of surveillance, profiling, punishment, containment and exclusion, further referring to them rhetorically as a 'digital poorhouse'⁶³.' She added that the 'digital poorhouse' offers a more inferior system that fails to meet

⁶² Dore, Ronald Philip. *Stock market capitalism: Welfare capitalism: Japan and Germany versus the Anglo-Saxons*. Oxford University Press on Demand, 2000.

⁶³ Eubanks Virginia. *Automating inequality: How high-tech tools profile, police, and punish the poor*. St. Martin's Press, 2018. These digital systems framed as a way to 'rationalize and streamline benefits', in reality go to 'profile, police and target the poor' (par 38). In her book that builds on her previous work on technology and social justice, she discusses how the outcomes of important decision making that shape lives have been given to 'sophisticated machines' instead of humans and explores the challenges and consequences in the United States. She documents the experiences of those "targeted by new tools of digital poverty management and face life-threatening consequences as a result", especially 'the low -income communities of colour further increasing inequalities (par 12).

the actual needs of the less privileged individual and increases inequalities. This emerging issue, though disturbing considering the stakes involved, has received very little attention especially from policymakers, tech companies and some researchers. Meanwhile, the focus has been on reaching targets related to budget saving, fraud detection and efficiency, a concern of the welfare community that tends to detach the technological aspects of the digital welfare state from the policy making and legal facets.

According to Philip Alston, ‘similar technologies, many of which are powered by machine learning and automated decision-making systems, turn the needs of the most vulnerable in our society into numbers and variables. Poverty and vulnerability are reduced to problems that can be “solved” or “fixed” by technological innovation.’⁶⁴ It is paradoxical, that systems created to protect social rights now violate the purpose for which they were designed. The human rights community, in curbing the negative effects of digitalization in our systems, makes it pivotal to address anomalies linked to the emergence of the surveillance state, the undermining of privacy, the highly discriminatory impact of many algorithms.

In light of such implications already evident in various countries, this concern should be tackled particularly by the lawmakers before what Philip Alston terms as a ‘digital dystopia’ is generated. In his ground-breaking report, he refers to this as a state in which the digital innovation, embraced by our societies, is used in an unbalanced approach to govern our systems.⁶⁵

The System Risk Indication (SyRI), an advanced version of the ‘Landelijke Stuurgroep Interventieteams’ (LSI), was one of the latest projects of the Dutch government designed to further institutionalize the cooperation between various authorities including the police, the tax authorities, the welfare authorities and the ministry of social affairs. This system was designed to process large amounts of data collected by various Dutch public authorities to identify those most likely to commit benefits fraud. This comprised a comparison between welfare authorities’ databases and that of other companies such as the drinking water company and real estate ownership companies to run investigations on individuals who were benefit recipients. The hitch however, is that subjects under scrutiny were individuals predominantly from more vulnerable groups and poorer neighbourhoods in Haarlem, Eindhoven, Capelle ann den IJssel and Rotterdam.⁶⁶ Moreover,

⁶⁴ UN Rapporteur Philip Alston, 2019- The digital welfare state.

⁶⁵ <https://www.law.nyu.edu/news/ideas/philip-alston-united-nations-digital-welfare-dystopia>

⁶⁶ <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Poverty/Amicusfinalversionsigned.pdf>

research shows that at the end of various projects set in motion, only a few out of the thousands were flagged as potential fraudsters. The ‘waterproof’ project, that provided welfare benefits for those without other means of income, in investigating for ‘living in’ fraud, arrived at 42 cases of fraud out of 63,000 individuals. In response to these happenings, claims were made by a coalition of welfare and digital rights NGOs to the District Court of the Hague. The court ruled in February 2020, that the SyRI violates the right to privacy and the Dutch government failed to maintain equilibrium between the right to privacy and the public interest in rolling out this project. It therefore considered the SyRI project to be disproportionate to its original aim.⁶⁷

In 1965, American legal scholar Charles Reich wrote in an article entitled ‘Individual rights and social welfare’, that in spite of the recognition of social security as a right around the 1930s in the United States, beneficiaries were still considered second-class citizens. In fact, they lacked ‘fundamental procedural safeguards against bureaucratic arbitrariness and faced serious infringements on their constitutional rights to privacy and equal protection under law.’⁶⁸ This is due to the perception of welfare as handouts given by the government that require strict supervision, subjecting recipients to ‘many forms of procedure and control not imposed on other citizens. No one will deny that fair and reasonable eligibility standards and effective protection against fraud are necessary when benefits are handed out. But the poor are too easily regulated.’ (Reich, 1965 p.1245)

Though governments often turn to digital tools for implementing political objectives, it is fundamental to maintain the underlying values, ethics and principles of the society. The welfare state’s key principles: the right to privacy, the right to social security amongst others should be upheld by all sectors of the digital welfare state including the business sector and entities involved in information technology. Additionally, automated processes should be carefully monitored to prevent any unfair disadvantages to people, breaching their rights and creating ‘human rights-free’ zones.

⁶⁷ <https://uitspraken.rechtspraak.nl/inziendocument?id=ECLI:NL:RBDHA:2020:1878>

⁶⁸ Reich, Charles A. "Individual rights and social welfare: the emerging legal issues."

Chapter III

Artificial Intelligence and Law.

3.0 Legal framework in the digital welfare state.

The legal apparatus forms the foundation of every society and its principles therefore should be imprinted in the formation of every area in our systems and hence, the digital welfare state.

Currently, Artificial Intelligence has been an important tool used by the states to generate incredible developments⁶⁹ in the last few decades which call for major consolidative measures that will build a more harmonious relation between law and this branch of technology in digital welfare state.

As established in the previous chapters technology in our modern world entails the use of computerized systems which have been present for decades although used in a limited context such as storage, electronic communication and research. An extension of this is characterized by the entry of AI which has been impactful and continues to advance rendering it attractive to both the private and public sectors. The areas of impact include human rights, criminal law, contract law, intellectual property, assist for judges, information retrieval and more recently robot lawyers. AI plays a major role in our societal structures and consequently, there is the need for understanding and then modelling a comprehensive legal interpretation⁷⁰ of the law in this field.

Much has been written on AI and law, especially in the context of the application of innovative AI in the legal field. Nonetheless, this discussion is from a more practical point of view, analysing the regulatory and policy landscape surrounding technology (also AI). This will be done through a rundown of regulations in correspondence to technology from a national and International point of view.

3.1 International legal framework.

In 2015, an AI and robotics centre was founded under the United Nations (UN) Interregional Crime and Justice research Institute (UNICRI) with the scope of ‘focusing expertise on Artificial

⁶⁹ Veritably, the special rapporteur confirms the welfare authorities as usually the ‘forefront of digital innovation within government’. He added that this is due to the large number of individuals interacting with the welfare state, the scope of welfare budgets and the opportunities offered by the new technologies to improve huge programs and bureaucracies. Brief by the UN Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights as amicus curiae in the case of NJCM c.s./De Staat de Nederlanden (SyRI) before the District Court of The Hague (case number. C/097550982/HA ZA 18/388) par 6.

⁷⁰ Rissland, Edwina L. "Artificial intelligence and law: Steppingstones to a model of legal reasoning."

Intelligence (AI) in the UN through a single Agency.’⁷¹ To further establish this, UNICRI ‘Signed the host country agreement for the opening of its Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics in the Hague, the Netherlands, in September 2017.’⁷² The task assigned to this body is to understand and address the risks and benefits of AI and robotics from the perspective of crime and security through awareness-raising, education, exchange of information, and harmonization of stakeholders. These include the International Criminal Police Organization (INTERPOL), the International Telecommunications Union (ITU), the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), the Foundation for Responsible Robotics, the World Economic Forum, Centre for Future Intelligence, amongst others.

According to the UNICRI director Ms Cindy J. Smith in September 2016, “The aim of the Centre is to enhance understanding of the risk-benefit duality of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics through improved coordination, knowledge collection and dissemination, awareness-raising and outreach activities. The Centre will open in The Hague, The Netherlands. The main outcome of the above initiative will be that all stakeholders, including policy makers and governmental officials, possess improved knowledge and understanding of both the risks and benefits of such technologies and that they commence discussion on these risks and potential solutions in an appropriate and balanced manner.”⁷³ This body continues to hold conferences, competitions, workshops, to obtain legal domain in the field.

Another agency of the UN worth considering is the International Telecommunication Union set to explore ‘the impact of AI providing a neutral platform for government, industry and academia to build a common understanding of the capabilities of emerging AI technologies and consequent needs for technical standardization and policy guidance.’

The Convention on Conventional Weapons and Lethal autonomous Weapons Systems (CCW) held informal meetings of experts and group of governmental experts’ meetings to regulate and eventually ban the use of certain weapons that could have negative effects on others including civilians. The meetings with various experts was held to evaluate the role of emerging technologies in law and if they could comply with International Humanitarian law, especially considering the

⁷¹ AI Policy – United Nations, FUTURE OF LIFE INSTITUTE, <https://futureoflife.org/ai-policy-united-nations/> (last visited Jan. 4, 2019), archived at <https://perma.cc/9CZ2-ETNX>.

⁷² Centre on Artificial Intelligence and Robotics, UNICRI, http://www.unicri.it/topics/ai_robotics/centre/

⁷³ The Hague, The Netherlands UNICRI Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics, UNICRI,

current level of autonomy.⁷⁴ Among the challenges raised in the CCW governmental meetings was the need for “retaining human control over weapons systems and the use of force and expressed support for developing new international law on lethal autonomous weapons systems.”⁷⁵

Considering these bodies on the international platform, it is obvious that there is a focus on exploring the growth and management of the technological field, as well as coordinating the relations between the law enforcement and security bodies, policy making, tech agencies, also on the rational level. However, there seems to be a lack of strong legal foundations in this field.

In regard to the data collected in the previous chapter, we have discovered that mainly AI or automated systems occasionally breach various individual and collective rights, reason why it is important to make mention and address some paramount law provisions that are infringed on by technology.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) adopted in 1948, is agreeably the foundation of International Human Rights Law. Hence, numerous legally binding International Human Rights treaties that recognize basic human rights and freedoms alienable and inherent to all people. It addresses injustices, conflicts, discrimination based on any form of diversity etc. These laws are obligations and duties assumed by binding states, that have adhered through international treaties, to protect and respect human rights.⁷⁶ The preamble states, ‘The General Assembly proclaims this declaration of human rights as a common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations. That every individual and every organ of society, keeping this Declaration constantly in mind, shall strive by teaching and educating to promote respect for these rights and freedoms and by both national and international progressive measures, to secure their universal and effective recognition and observance, both among the peoples of Member States themselves and among the peoples of territories under their jurisdiction.’⁷⁷

Several UDHR provisions indirectly question the abuse and violations piloted by automated systems, potentially autocratic tools used in undermining the autonomy, personhood and self-determination of individuals in our welfare states:

⁷⁴ Michael W. Meier, *Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (Laws): Conducting a Comprehensive Weapons Review*, 30

⁷⁵ UN: *Decisive Action Needed to Ban Killer Robots – Before It’s Too Late*, AMNESTY INTERNATIONAL (Aug. 27, 2018),

⁷⁶ Baderin, Mashood A., and Manisuli Ssenyonjo. "Development of International Human Rights Law before and after the UDHR."

⁷⁷ <https://www.un.org/en/universal-declaration-human-rights/>

“Article 1. All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.

Article 2. Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.

Article 3. Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person.

Article 6. Everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law.

Article 7. All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination.

Article 22. Everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security and is entitled to realization, through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality.

Article 25. (1) Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control.

(2) Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection.

Article 26. (1) Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit.

(2) Education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding,

tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace (...)"

Article 25, in particular refers to typical welfare state principles, mentioning security in case of unfortunate occurrences to the citizen and social protection. The importance of identity is also portrayed in article 6, with the right to recognition as an individual before the law. Other principles mentioned are the right to be treated equally irrespective of cultural, ethnic backgrounds or political stands.

The UN Declaration on the Right to Development (OHCHR)⁷⁸, adopted by the UN General assembly in 1986, is also worth discussing. The declaration explicitly provides in article 1, that the right to development is an inalienable human right, directed to individuals and people (and not governments), to engage and enjoy social, economic, cultural and political development, where human rights and fundamental freedoms are realized. It goes on to emphasize on people, as the central subject and beneficiary of development (article 2). In addition to this, it acknowledges the responsibility of the state in creating a legally conducive and favourable platform for the materialisation of this description of development.

Article 2.3 mentions that States have the right and the duty to formulate appropriate national development policies that aim at constantly improving the well-being of the entire population, on the 'basis of their active, free and meaningful participation in development and in the fair distribution of the benefits resulting therefrom'.

Article 3.1. "States have the primary responsibility for the creation of national and international conditions favourable to the realization of the right to development.

3.2. The realization of the right to development requires full respect for the principles of international law concerning friendly relations and co-operation among States in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations.

3.3. States have the duty to co-operate with each other in ensuring development and eliminating obstacles to development. States should realize their rights and fulfil their duties in such a manner as to promote a new international economic order based on sovereign equality, interdependence, mutual

⁷⁸<https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/righttodevelopment.aspx#:~:text=1.,freedoms%20can%20be%20fully%20realized.>

interest and co-operation among all States, as well as to encourage the observance and realization of human rights.”

Further on, this declaration highlights the need for a collective co-operation between states to promote and consolidate the universal respect and observation of these rights (Article 6.1); Articles 6.2 and 6.3 affirm the ‘indivisible and interdependence between the rights and fundamental freedoms’, motive for which equal attention should be paid especially in their implementation. Obstacles birthed from a shortfall of upholding civil, political, economic and social rights must be expelled. Most vital to us is the call taken on the national level the “necessary measures for the realization of the right to development and ensure, inter alia , equality of opportunity for all in their access to basic resources, education, health services, food, housing, employment and the fair distribution of income. Effective measures should be undertaken to ensure that women have an active role in the development process. Appropriate economic and social reforms should be carried out with a view of eradicating all social injustices.” (Article 8.1)

The Committee of Economic and Social Rights (CESCR) also confirmed the State’s duties in regulating national and foreign businesses, ensuring their activities do not have adverse effects on basic rights. It states that “the obligation to respect economic, social and cultural rights is violated when States parties prioritize the interests of business entities over Covenant rights without justification, or when they pursue policies that negatively affect such rights. (General Comment No. 24)⁷⁹

Although there is no direct mention of technology, the member states, in adopting and interpreting these laws and making policies, should pay more attention to public or private entities in Information and Communication Technology. As recommended by the UN high level report on Digital cooperation, “there is an urgent need to examine how time-honoured human rights frameworks and conventions – and the obligations that flow from those commitments – can guide actions and policies relating to digital cooperation and digital technology, (...)how human rights can be meaningfully applied to ensure that no gaps in protection are caused by new and emerging digital technologies.”⁸⁰ Every local, private, multinational and public body is accountable for the systems integrated in their activities.

⁷⁹ <https://www.refworld.org/docid/5beacba4.html>

⁸⁰ <https://www.un.org/en/pdfs/DigitalCooperation-report-for%20web.pdf>

3.2 Regional legal framework.

Still on the purpose of our discussion on automation and the challenges incurred on individual and collective rights, the next important factor is how state parties have translated these rights into regional and national laws. Notably, this occurs depending on the level of development, particularly economical. This section outlines the provisions of a few regional communities in the field of digital innovation.

The Organization of the American States (OAS), is a continental organization founded in 1948 to consolidate the relationship between the countries in the western hemisphere (northern and southern America). The main goals are to harness the autonomy of the region and limiting foreign intervention through economic, cultural and social development.⁸¹ In 2018, the OAS in a report, called on the banking section of the Caribbean and Latin America to “prioritize the development of capacities using emerging digital technologies, which have an important potential in the optimization of resources destined for detection and prevention.” [52] It found that “49% of banking entities are still not implementing tools, controls or processes using Emerging Digital Technologies, such as Big Data, Machine Learning or Artificial Intelligence. These are all very important for the prevention of cyber- attacks or defining suspect patterns associated with fraud, amongst other detection capabilities.” This stresses on how we are being encouraged to amalgamate technological innovation in our societies and a reason why sturdy laws should be put in place on the various levels of governance.

On the 4th of October 2018, the European ethical Charter on the use of Artificial Intelligence in Judicial Systems and their Environment (The European Ethical Charter)⁸², was established by the European Commission for the Efficiency of Justice(CEPEJ) of the Council of Europe (CoE), an International body of 47 States (27 of which are European), that focuses mainly on Human Rights. The Charter was designed for private and public stakeholders responsible for designing and deploying AI tools and services. Also, it outlines five ethical principles meant to guide policy makers, legislators and justice professionals in working with artificial intelligence followed by an in-depth study on the use of AI in judicial systems within member states with focus on applications processing judicial decisions and data.

⁸¹ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Organization-of-American-States>

⁸² European Ethical Charter on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Judicial Systems and Their Environment (Dec. 3/4, 2018), European Commission for the Efficiency of Justice (CEPEJ)

These principles mentioned include:

- 1-The respect for fundamental rights during the design and implementation of AI
- 2-The principle of non-discrimination
- 3-Quality and security when processing judicial decisions and data (the use of certified codes, secured technological environments)
- 4-Transparency, impartiality, and fairness
- 5- The principle of “Under user control” that precludes a prescriptive approach and ensures users are informed and in control of their choices.⁸³

The European Parliament’s Resolution on Civil Law Rules on Robotics (2017) is a legislative initiative resolution that sets out AI and robotics legislative and non-legislative acts to the European Commission.⁸⁴ The proposals made to the commission include the need for legislative instrument providing civil law rules on the liability of robots and AI, defining technology and AI related systems, establishing an EU Agency for Robotics and Artificial Intelligence, a code of conduct for engineers, for reviewing robotics protocols and even model licenses for designers. In 2018, the European Commission also established the ‘Artificial Intelligence of Europe’⁸⁵, a Communication with the scope of finding the best methods of maximizing the opportunities of AI and addressing the challenges it poses in our societies. It continues to emphasize on the importance of upholding the community’s values and fundamental human rights.

In December 2018, the High-Level expert group on Artificial intelligence (AI HLEG) comprised of fifty-two experts appointed by the EU commission, provided a draft on AI ethic guidelines. With the help of these guidelines, the construction of trustworthy AI is expected, that will “respect fundamental rights, applicable regulations and core principles and values, ensuring an “ethical purpose,” and “be technically robust and reliable since, even with good intentions, a lack of technological mastery can cause unintentional harm.”⁸⁶

⁸³ MSI-AUT, A Study of the Implications of Advanced Digital Technologies (Including AI Systems) for the Concept of Responsibility Within a Human Rights Framework (Nov. 9, 2018).

⁸⁴ European Parliament Resolution of 16 February 2017 with Recommendations to the Commission on Civil Law Rules on Robotics (2015/2103(INL))

⁸⁵ See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2018%3A237%3AFIN>

⁸⁶ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, EUROPEAN COMMISSION, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/high-level-expert-group-artificial-intelligence> (last updated Oct. 29, 2018), archived at <http://perma.cc/4RHT-N4A7>.

Another vital legal piece is the General Data Processing Regulation (GDPR), a law on data protection and privacy of the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA), that entered into force on the 25th of May 2018. The GDPR consists of 11 chapters that regulate the local and international use of personal data belonging to individuals residing in its territory (Territorial scope Article 3.1)⁸⁷; this added to the bargain, gives EU residents more control over their own data and promotes transparency. Another goal achieved with this is the simplification and unification of the regulatory field pertaining to this subject.

This regulation explicitly mentions the “processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of a filing system.” (Article 2.1) The Article 13 of the GDPR covers the “Information to be provided where personal data are collected from the data subject.” Where data subject is another name for the individual, this rule requires that all information having to do with data retrieval are stated. These may include the “identity and contact details of the controller i.e. the legal person, authority or body that determines the purpose and the means by which data is processed. Further information includes contact details of protection officer (Article 13.1); the final destination of retrieved data and the period for which data will be stored (Article 13.2a) and the existence of automated decision making (Article 13.2f). The Right to access of the data subject is mentioned in Article 15, granting the individual the right to know if their personal data is being processed, gain access to it and other related information such as the categories of personal data concerned (Article 15. 1b) and the source of data in cases where it was not collected directly from the data source.”

Most importantly, the GDPR states that “the data subjects shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her” (Article 22.1); this is applicable where necessary, where authorised by the Union or member states or where consent has previously been expressed by a provision that eliminates hints of dictatorship in this field. The regulation further assigns responsibility to the controller based on the principle of accountability. In more practical terms, it states that ‘appropriate technical and organizational measures should be taken by him or her to guarantee compliance with the regulation’s measures.’ (Article 24)

⁸⁷ <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-15-gdpr/>

In the event of data breach, the controller is obliged to report to supervisory authorities not later than 72 hours after becoming aware of it, if possible, “unless the personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.” (Article 33)

The GDPR is one of the most detailed regulations on the use of automated systems and the protection of the right to privacy in the world. Its 99 articles are extended to the rightful use of processors and their security to guarantee the rights of the data subjects; the establishment of data protection mechanisms that will provide seals demonstrating compliance to the regulations; procedural rights to effective judicial remedy; cooperation between lead supervisory and other supervisory authorities etc.

European member states additionally have other collaborations and legal provisions such as the Declaration of Cooperation on Artificial Intelligence and the European Supervisory Authorities Report to further develop a European approach to AI and monitor the exercise of automation in financial advice.⁸⁸ The replication of such detailed and structured regulations in other regional communities would be advantageous to assure security in their territories. Where clear regulations are established, accountability, transparency and progressive development can be guaranteed.

3.3 Examples of Legal Frameworks on Technology and Artificial Intelligence on the National level (Canada, Kenya and India)

According to a 2019 survey propelled by the Law Library of Congress⁸⁹ (The Global Research Directorate) on the regulations of Artificial Intelligence in selected Jurisdictions⁹⁰, although most states in discussing technology or automated systems consider various legal issues, such as “data protection and privacy, transparency, human oversight, surveillance, public administration and services, autonomous vehicles, and lethal autonomous weapons systems, the most advanced regulations were found in the area of autonomous vehicles, in particular for the testing of such vehicles.” A substantial number of countries have developed, or are in the process of developing a national AI or digital strategy and action plan, most of which highlight the need to expand ethical and legal frameworks to make sure AI is rightfully developed and applied in alignment to the values and fundamental rights adopted in the country, in order to avoid a quagmire in the near future.

⁸⁸ Joint Committee Of The European Supervisory Authorities, Joint Committee Report On The Results Of The Monitoring Exercise On ‘Automation In Financial Advice

⁸⁹ <https://www.loc.gov/law/about/>

⁹⁰ <https://www.loc.gov/law/help/artificial-intelligence/regulation-artificial-intelligence.pdf>

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National AI Strategies

- Strategy/Plan in place
- Part of Overall Digital/Development Strategy
- Currently Developing Strategy
- No National Strategy
- Countries not in Study

Sources: Created by the LawLibrary of Congress based on information provided in LawLibrary of Congress, *Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in Selected Jurisdictions* (Jan. 2019), <https://www.loc.gov/whelp/artificial-intelligence/index.php>

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Position on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems

- Adoption of Political Declaration
- Negotiate Treaty
- No action necessary at this time
- Countries not in Study
- Ban Supported
- Further Study/Definitions needed
- No Official Position

Source: Created by the LawLibrary of Congress based on information provided in Law Library of Congress, *Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in Selected Jurisdictions* (Jan. 2019), <https://www.loc.gov/law/help/artificial-intelligence/index.php>

Canada, known to have the second largest tech sector outside the Silicon Valley and one of the top leaders in AI⁹¹, was the first country to launch a national AI strategy in 2017. The Centre for International Governance and Innovation stated in an article tackling ‘the deficit behind the Canadian Artificial Intelligence’⁹², that the country had been concentrating extensively on funding and promoting research and lagging behind where governance in AI is concerned .i.e. the development of efficient government structures and emanating regulations.

In fact, the Pan -Canadian Artificial Intelligence strategy, led by the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research (CIFAR), centres its work on building further the Canadian AI research based ecosystem by increasing the AI researchers and skilled graduates, developing ‘global thought

⁹¹ Carole J. Piovesan et al., *Artificial Intelligence: The Year in Review*, MCCARTHY TÉTRAULT (Jan. 16, 2018)

⁹² <https://www.cigionline.org/articles/policy-deficit-behind-canadian-artificial-intelligence>

leadership on the economic, ethical, policy and legal implications of advances in AI and supporting a national community in the field.⁹³

In relation to regulatory frameworks, Canada has a few provisions on automated vehicles but shared responsibility between federal, provinces and territorial governments. The Provinces and territories have been given the jurisdiction to approve trials done in their territory. The survey indicates that Quebec and Ontario have enacted changes to allow test drives of automated vehicles.

The Personal Information Protection and Electronic documents Act (PIPEDA), is a federal privacy law enacted to protect personal data⁹⁴. It is mainly focused on individual consent. Persons must give organizations consent to collect, use and process their personal data (the Privacy Commissioner of Canada). In February 2018, the House of Commons Standing Committee on Access to Information, Privacy and Ethics, recommended that the PIPEDA be updated, this was influenced by the direction set by the EU's GDPR⁹⁵. It expressed concerns over the transparency of AI decision-making i.e. how it works and the data collection; and the possible risk of algorithms using personal information to "perpetuate prejudices or discriminatory practices." The committee further recommended that appropriate measures be taken to improve algorithmic transparency.⁹⁶ In response to these, the office of the Privacy Commissioner of Canada presented two guidance documents intended to support in collecting 'meaning' consent and help organizations abide by the regulations.⁹⁷

According to the Cyber Justice Laboratory of the University of Montreal, the directive on Automated Decision-making of the 26th November 2018, outlines "the responsibilities of federal institutions using AI-automated decision systems, supporting a host of policies in the federal public administration. The directive aims at helping to better understand and better ensure an ethical and responsible implementation of AI. Compliance with its requirements, is expected from all federal institutions by no later than April 1, 2020."⁹⁸ It also applies to some processors that deal with external services and recommendations about a particular client, or whether an application should be approved or denied. It provides the 'Algorithmic Impact Assessment' questionnaire, to be

⁹³ Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy, Canadian Institute For Advanced Research (CIFAR)

⁹⁴ Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act, S.C. 2000

⁹⁵ Standing Committee On Access To Information, Privacy And Ethics, Towards Privacy By Design: Review Of The Personal Information Protection And Electronic Documents Act (Feb. 2018)

⁹⁶ The report defines "algorithmic transparency" as "when users have complete information about the workings of the artificial intelligence programs behind the websites they visit, the data they collect and how they are used."

⁹⁷ Press Release, Office of the Privacy Commissioner of Canada, Privacy Commissioner Issues New Guidance to Help Address Consent Challenges in the Digital Age (May 24, 2018),

⁹⁸ Canada Treasury Board's Directive on Automated Decision-Making, CYBERJUSTICE LABORATORY (Nov. 25, 2018)

completed before producing automated decision system applied in the federal administration and “designed to help federal institutions assess and mitigate the risks associated with deploying an automated decision system.”

Adopting AI strategies aimed to expand AI research, searching for talent and supporting innovations, organizing digital summits with professionals from different sectors including business, open research institutes etc. These form the most common approach in dealing with AI so far. In most European countries, the strategies by which AI technologies are being built should be based on the values of the GDPR. Germany has the Data ethics commission, composed of sixteen experts from the fields of medicine, law, computer science, statistics, economics, theology, ethics, journalism aimed to propose ethical guidelines for data policy, algorithms, artificial intelligence; digital innovation; recommendations and regulatory proposals to the German government.⁹⁹

Furthermore, in this chapter, it is only right to understand the regulatory structure in Kenya and India, which will be the bedrock of the rest of our study. In February 2018, the Kenyan government founded an eleven-member blockchain and AI task force, comprised of representatives from academia, research institutions and the local technology sector directly accountable to the Cabinet Secretary for Information, Communications and Technology¹⁰⁰. Additionally, it “ provided the roadmap to contextualize on the application of these emerging technologies in the areas of financial inclusion, cybersecurity, land tilting, election process, single digital identity and overall public service delivery,” The main goal of the task force is to “make recommendations on how the government can leverage on the emerging technologies in the next five years, with other key milestones in 2027 and 2032.”

According to the Law Library of Congress survey, India generally has no laws or government issued guidelines on Artificial Intelligence but in 2018, national strategies were developed in this field. Examples are the Artificial Intelligence task force¹⁰¹, the Niti Aayog Discussion Paper on a

⁹⁹ BMI & BMJV, THE FEDERAL GOVERNMENT’S KEY QUESTIONS TO THE DATA ETHICS COMMISSION (June 5, 2018), <https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/EN/themen/it-digital-policy/key-questions-Data-Ethics-commission.pdf?blob=publicationFile&v=4>, archived at <http://perma.cc/H97L-G7BB>.

¹⁰⁰ Kenya Govt Unveils 11 Member Blockchain & AI Taskforce Headed by Bitange Ndemo, THE KENYAN WALL STREET (Feb. 28, 2018)

¹⁰¹ Press Release, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Commerce and Industry Minister Sets Up Task Force on Artificial Intelligence for Economic Transformation (Aug. 25, 2017)

National AI Strategy¹⁰², committees established by the ministry of information to promote studies on AI, a multi-stakeholder task force with the aim of examining AI in various fields, getting to know their challenges and possible solutions; studying AI in the context of citizen centric services, data platforms, skilling etc; and analysing the implications of AI on national security respectively.

Apropos to regulation on data protection in India, a Data Protection of Personal Data Bill was drafted on July 27th, 2018 by the Justice B.N. Srikrishna Committee (India's Committee of Experts)¹⁰³. It sets out some rights, similar to the GDPR but excludes the protection of rights against automated decision-making. In point of fact, the Centre for Internet and Society stated in an analysis that "the Bill creates a framework to address harms arising out of AI, but does not empower the individual to decide how their data is processed and remains silent on the issue of 'black box' algorithms." In addition the Bill "is focused on placing the responsibility on companies to prevent harm."¹⁰⁴ The Committee, in a report accompanying the Bill, clarified that there was legitimacy behind these rights in question because they curbed the harms that could be done due to prejudice and discrimination particularly when it lacks human review. This factor should be incorporated through structured changes that can also be monitored closely, enough to detect any type of bias and still cover the individual's agency.

3.4 Conclusion

In concluding on the regulations on AI in our digital welfare state, we have to acknowledge some challenges that emerge in result of an increase in the development and complexity in this field, rendering it somewhat difficult to determine factors that contribute to certain mishaps. In case of a cyberattack or data breach, due to the various processes and voluminous amounts of data, deducing information such as when an attack took place, the exact source of the malfunctioning or the identification of data subjects, may seem arduous. Obtaining effective consent may also appear challenging in this regard.

¹⁰² Why We Need to Have Regulation and Legislation on AI and Quick, THE INDIAN EXPRESS (July 31, 2018), <https://indianexpress.com/article/technology/opinion-technology/why-we-need-to-have-regulation-and-legislation-on-artificial-intelligence-quick-5151401/>

¹⁰³ Personal Data Protection Bill, 2018, http://meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/Personal_Data_Protection_Bill,2018.pdf, archived at <https://perma.cc/GN5K-NJNG>.

¹⁰⁴ Committee Of Experts Under The Chairmanship Of Justice B.N. Srikrishna, supra note at 83, at 74-5.

It is faultless, that digital technologies including artificial intelligence are factors that promote the benefits presented by the welfare state. However, considering the expansion of technology in recent times it is only logic that the legal sectors are involved with the development of technology in the welfare state. If the laws enacted would explicitly cover individual rights, implement incentives, facilitate and ensure that the state encourages accountability from businesses and entities managing automated systems, the welfare state will be in a better position to offer a decent standard of living, fulfilling its duties towards citizens.

Chapter IV

4.0 Automated Identification Systems

Identity is a fundamental right that defines each person and cannot be separated from the individual personality. This important tie with identity creates the individual's anthropological, philosophical, social and juridical profile; reason why the subject of identification comes to relevance in our society.¹⁰⁵

Identification is obtained through identity- subject mechanisms that, when scrutinized, reveal an amount of complexity and intricacy, especially when examined through a legal perspective. In this regard, the continuous evolving of technological operations in identification has introduced innovation and advancement in the field. Systems that are programmed to autonomously identify persons. We are referring mainly to the use of biometric data, a more sophisticated but effective mechanism that operates with very personal characteristics. These physiological traits include face recognition, iris recognition, speaker identification; making the individual a “walking identification password.”¹⁰⁶ Such means of identification have become beneficial in numerous sectors overtime including public, private entities and organizations (NGOs, International Organizations etc.)

As clarified in previous chapters, these automated systems have proven to occasionally have high tendencies of data breach, discriminations, that infringe fundamental rights, diluting to an unacceptable degree, the human element of the welfare state. This is not a direct consequence of underdevelopment, neither is it an exclusive characteristic of technologically advanced countries; in fact, the attributes of advanced tech and AI may have these same consequences in most countries where it is applied if not curbed. These effects manifest especially where there is a deficiency in furnishing clear-cut provisions that control such fields and calls for proper legal attention.

India and Kenya faced similar challenges with national identification systems set in motion by their governments to facilitate activities of the welfare state. We compare two case studies of automated systems in these countries with very different backgrounds and perspectives, to evince the pertinent, transversal nature of the legal challenges that emerge with the use of biometric data for identification purposes.

¹⁰⁵ Formici, Giulia. "Sistemi di riconoscimento e dati biometrici: una nuova sfida per i Legislatori e le Corti."

¹⁰⁶ Refer to chapter II. Artificial Intelligence as a tool in the digital welfare state.

A) Kenya

4.1.1 Kenyan legal system

Kenya has a common law system based on its history as a British colony. The Constitution, enacted in 1963, is the highest form of law in the country. The government of the Republic of Kenya consists of 47 counties, characterized by semi-autonomous governments. The national government, composed of the three arms, executive, judiciary and legislature, are regulated by the constitution of Kenya, last amended in 2010. The judicial structure consists of the Court of Appeal (also the highest court of Kenya), the High Courts and the Subordinate Courts.

Chapter 4 of the Kenyan Constitution lays out the Bill of Rights which encompasses the framework for Social, economic and cultural policies “recognising and protecting human rights and fundamental freedoms to preserve the dignity of individuals and communities, and to promote social justice and the realisation of the potential of all human beings.”¹⁰⁷ The Bill covers a vast array of rights including the right to life, the protection of human dignity, freedom and security of the persons, privacy, the right to fair administrative action etc. These articles also provide normative implications that guide the application and interpretations of laws. As mentioned previously, the Kenyan legal framework does not explicitly mention technology but is conscious of building systems that respect and adhere to the constitution.

4.1.2 The Kenyan Case Study: The Nubian Rights Forum & 2 others v Attorney-General & 6 others; Child Welfare Society & 8 others (Interested Parties); Centre for Intellectual Property & Information Technology (Proposed Amicus Curiae) [2019].

- Background and facts.

The Statute Law (Miscellaneous Act) No.18 of 2018 was voted in November 2018 and entered into force on the 18th January 2019. This Act amended several provisions including the Registration of Person’s Act (also chapter 107 of the Laws of Kenya), curated to make provisions for the registration of persons and for the issue of identity cards, and for purposes connected therewith.”¹⁰⁸ The amendments to this Act institute the National Integrated Information Management System

¹⁰⁷ [https://kenyanconstitution.manjemedia.com/the-bill-of-rights/#:~:text=\(1\)%20The%20Bill%20of%20Rights%20applies%20to%20all%20law%20and,the%20right%20or%20fundamental%20freedom.&text=\(b\)%20the%20spirit%2C%20purport,of%20the%20Bill%20of%20Rights.](https://kenyanconstitution.manjemedia.com/the-bill-of-rights/#:~:text=(1)%20The%20Bill%20of%20Rights%20applies%20to%20all%20law%20and,the%20right%20or%20fundamental%20freedom.&text=(b)%20the%20spirit%2C%20purport,of%20the%20Bill%20of%20Rights.)

¹⁰⁸ <http://kenyalaw.org/kl/fileadmin/pdfdownloads/Acts/RegistrationofPersonsActCap.%20107.pdf>

(NIIMS), a centralized repository that consists of the personal data of all Kenyan citizens and foreigners living in the country.

In opposition to this, the Nubian Rights Forum¹⁰⁹, the Kenya Human Rights Commission¹¹⁰ and the Kenya National Commission on Human Rights¹¹¹ respectively filed three separate petitions to the Constitutional and Human Rights Division of the High Court of Kenya in Nairobi¹¹². These petitions were subsequently consolidated by the bench for hearing. Additionally, nine other parties were enjoined as interested parties. These include the Child Welfare Society, Ajibika Society, Muslims for Human Rights, Haki Centre, Law Society of Kenya, Inform Action, Bunge La Mwananchi, International Policy Group and Terror Victims Support Initiative.

The seven respondents in this consolidated petition were the Honourable Attorney General; the Cabinet Secretary, Ministry of Interior and Co-ordination of National Government; the Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Interior and Co-ordination of National Government; the Director of National Registration; the Cabinet Secretary for Information, Communication and Technology; the Speaker of the National Assembly, and the Kenya Law Reform Commission.

The petitioners expressed their grievances on the amendments impugned in the Registration of Persons Act, describing them as contrary to the provisions made by the constitution and the fundamental rights upheld by it. The key areas of contention encompass the exclusion and prejudice against the Nubian population¹¹³, deprived of identification cards and/or birth certificates, thus, disadvantaged as far as the NIIMS scheme is concerned by the unequal field of play; the absence of public consent or participation in the introduction and passing of the said amendments; the lack of sufficient or adequate safeguards for the security of data and/or personal information intended for collection under the NIIMS system, especially with the extraction of personal information and biometric data through DNA- Deoxyribonucleic Acid¹¹⁴ and “Global Positioning System co-

¹⁰⁹The Nubian rights forum is part of a movement that advocates the rights of the Nubian Ethnic minority in Kenya. See <http://nubianrightsforum.org/>

¹¹⁰ The Kenya human rights commission works on the community level to ensure the entrenchment of a human rights and democratic culture in Kenya. See <https://www.khrc.or.ke/about-us.html>

¹¹¹ This is an independent Human Rights Commission created by the Article 59 of the Kenyan Constitution. It monitors the respect of human rights in the country and provides key leadership to move the country towards a Human Rights State. <https://www.knchr.org/About-Us/Establishment>

¹¹² The Kenyan Case between the Nubian Rights Forum & 2 others v Attorney-General & 6 others; Child Welfare Society & 8 others (Interested Parties); Centre for Intellectual Property & Information Technology (Proposed Amicus Curiae) [2019]. <http://kenyalaw.org/caselaw/cases/view/172447/>

¹¹³ The Nubian community in Kenya were Sudanese inhabitants brought by the British colonists to the territory primarily as soldiers.

¹¹⁴ ..the hereditary material in humans and almost all other organisms that contains your unique genetic code.

ordinates (GPS)”¹¹⁵ without consent, such that the right to privacy guaranteed pursuant to Article 31 of the Constitution, is infringed and/or threatened. Another interesting factor that was contested, was the fact that the amendments challenged were published through an omnibus legislation¹¹⁶ and in the ‘Gazette Notice’ and were drawn up in such a way as to obscure the amendments from the public. In fact, the amendments challenged were published alongside sixty-seven other pieces of legislation, irrespective of the substantive nature and seriousness of the provisions amended. The petitioners further declared unconstitutional, the sections 3, 5 and 9 of the Registered Person’s Act amended by the Miscellaneous Law Act.¹¹⁷ Moreover, orders were sought to implement the decisions of the African Commission on Human Rights and the African Committee on the Rights and Welfare of the Child in the cases of Nubian Community of Kenya v. Kenya¹¹⁸ and Children of Nubian Descent v. Kenya,¹¹⁹ before commencing the NIIMS registration process. The decision declared that processes subjecting communities such as the Nubian Community to differential treatments during registration result in infringement of their personal right to equality and freedom from non-discrimination.

In February 2019, the petitioners simultaneously filed through notice of motion¹²⁰, applications for various conservatory orders. These orders reiterated the need for the court to obstruct temporarily, the implementation of the amendments made to the Registration of Persons Act (CAP. 107 Laws of Kenya vide Statute Law (Miscellaneous Amendment) Act No. 18 of 2018)¹²¹, at least till the hearing of the Court: “That the Respondents, by themselves, their employees, agents and/or servants be prohibited from installing and operationalizing the NIIMS process in any manner howsoever until policy, legal and institutional frameworks compliant with the Constitution are put in place.”

¹¹⁵ Section 3 and 5 (g) of Registration of Persons Act

¹¹⁶ A proposed law that covers a number of diverse or unrelated topics.

¹¹⁷Section 3 particularly covers interpretations regarding the Registration of Persons Act, Section 5 covers the introduction of a register containing all information and Section 9 covers the establishment of a national Integrated Identity Management System. <http://kenyalaw.org/kl/fileadmin/pdfdownloads/AmendmentActs/2018/StatuteLawMiscellaneousNo18of2018.pdf>

¹¹⁸ The African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights found that Kenya’s arbitrary procedures that restrict access to identity documents based on an individuals’ religious or ethnic identity violated the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights. For more info: <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/litigation/nubian-community-kenya-v-kenya#:~:text=The%20Nubian%20community%20of%20Kenya,the%20British%20colonial%20armed%20forces.>

¹¹⁹ The African Committee of Experts on the Rights and Welfare of the Child found that such discrimination leading to statelessness violates African human rights standards. <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/litigation/children-nubian-descent-kenya-v-kenya>

¹²⁰ A written documentation to the court requesting the court to issue a ruling or order on a legal matter. The motions are the first step a party must take before the court can weigh in on a legal matter.

¹²¹ Also see

http://www.kenyalaw.org/kl/fileadmin/pdfdownloads/AmendmentActs/2018/StatuteLaw_MiscellaneousAmendments_Act_2018.pdf

The applications made via notice of motion also requested that the petitions be heard on a priority basis.

The petitioners explained that this is justified by the mandatory nature of the impugned provisions that require that all citizens including children to submit their personal information. The amendments however did not include important details such as the definition for personal information, standards and principles to be observed, who gathers the information etc. They could risk exposing their data in case of cyberattacks or any other complication due to the inadequate security guarantee to citizens and tangible legislation and policy on data protection, especially with the launch of a centralized repository like the NIIMS. They contended that the identification system would increasingly need additional information that may be irrelevant to the identification of persons and unnecessarily invasive.

The application mentions the potential threat of violation to other rights and freedoms. Furthermore, all petitioners stated that the amendments introduced to sections 3, 5 and 9 of the Registration of Person's Act are illegal, un-procedural and null, since they 'violate several provisions of the Constitution, particularly Article 31 on the right to privacy and Articles 10¹²² and Article 118¹²³ on national values and public participation.'

In opposition to this, the respondents contend that the petitions are premised on misconceptions that negate the substance and object of the NIIMS systems. In their perspective, the amendments were legislated respecting the boundaries of a 'proper and justified legislative process.' Firstly, the NIIMS was created to promote efficient administration and co-ordination, facilitate accountability and the management and allocation of State resources (Art 201 and 203 of Kenyan constitution) through a centralized database that 'captures and stores' the personal information and biometric data of citizens. More importantly, the principal aim was to enable them access benefits they were entitled to and contrary to the implications of the petitioners, this is meant to ease the registration and identification of individuals, improving security of the country by authenticating and verifying identities. The objectives of the Act were also directed to address duplication in registration; detection and prevention of fraud; impersonation and other criminal activities. Additionally, they affirmed the availability of data protection provisions prior to the amendments under various

¹²² The Kenyan Constitution covers the national values and principles of governance 'binds state organs, public officers and all persons whenever any of them applies or interprets the constitution, enacts any law or implements public policy decisions.'

¹²³ The constitution addresses 'the responsibility of the parliament to conduct its business in an open manner, facilitating public participation and its seating unless justifiable reasons are given.'

statutes including section 83 of the Kenyan Information and Communications Act¹²⁴, Section 20 of the Computer misuse and Cyber Crimes Act (2018)¹²⁵, the Access to Information Act¹²⁶ and the Registration of persons' Act.

The indictment that parliamentary procedures were flouted was countered especially with regards to the absence of public participation (Art 118.2 Constitution). This important step of the law-making process may concern the citizens directly, or indirectly through their representatives. Furthermore, they insisted that the Ministry of Interior and Co-ordination of the National Government involved public participation extensively through the publication of articles in newspapers and the Kenya Gazette, active online engagements and live coverages of persons spearheading the initiatives.

Disapproving the procedures to enacting the Amendment Act was considered as 'questioning' the competency of the parliament and ultimately the legislative branch of governance. The opposition referred to this approach as a violation of the Article 109 of the Kenyan Constitution, that mandates the parliament to enact, amend and repeal laws unless such is rebutted appropriately. This confirms the constitutionality of the Miscellaneous Amendment Act no.18. Also, they added that the petitioners failed to demonstrate exceptional circumstances to warrant the grant of the conservatory orders. Furthermore, they clarified that a NIIMS pilot programme had already commenced with the deployment of about 50,000 registration officers. Freezing thus the launch of the programme would affect public interest immensely and offend Article 201(d) of the constitution that instructs the prudent and reasonable use of public funds.¹²⁷

Ulterior submissions from both parties were made consisting of cited decided cases either to affirm their support for the implementation of the conservatory orders stating that respondents excluded, everyone else would suffer some form of prejudice if the conservatory orders are not implemented; or to oppose the petitioners applications for these orders in their respective written and oral orders.

Court analysis and disposition.

The court analysed the petitions and submissions of both parties and established two main issues to determine: if pending the answer to the petitions, the amendments to the Registration of Persons Act

¹²⁴ An Act of parliament to provide for the establishment of the Communications Commissions of Kenya, to facilitate the development of ICT. The Commission shall be to licence and regulate postal, information and communication services in accordance with the provisions of this Act.

¹²⁵ Also known as the computer and cybercrime Bill. Section 83 touches on the procedures set up to register licences under the Act. These include the application, implementation and enforcement of the use of the license by law. This Bill is a detailed

¹²⁶ Enacted in 2016, it gives effect to the right to access information (Art 35 of constitution)

¹²⁷ Article 201 lays out principles guiding all aspects of finance.

(also miscellaneous amendment Act No. 18 of 2018) should be suspended; and if the respondents should be restrained from installing and implementing the National Integrated Information Management system (NIIMS).

After affirming its power to grant conservatory orders (Art 23 (c) of the constitution)¹²⁸, considering the applicable principles for such grant and cases¹²⁹, bearing in mind the public interest, the constitutional values, and the proportionate magnitudes and priority levels attributable to the causes; the court made some observations and clarifications prior to its disposition. These include the likelihood of a prima facie case¹³⁰; considering the respondent's evidence regarding the existence of current laws on privacy, data protection and security as substantial although suspended temporarily¹³¹; defining the 'public interest',¹³² the relevance of striking a balance with the 'competing public interest' between an efficient and organized registration of persons system and the protection of rights and freedoms.

In its disposition, dated April 1st, 2018, the Court found that irrespective of the prima facie case made regarding some elements of the petition, it still did not find it appropriate to issue the conservatory orders on the terms prayed. However, the Court laid out other orders to be respected pending the hearing and determination of the consolidated petitions: First of all, the Deoxyribonucleic Acid- DNA)¹³³ included as a unique biometric data (section 3 & 5(g) Registration of Persons Act) is temporarily suspended. All other unique identifiers described in the provisions are left active. Secondly, the suspension of the definition and inclusion of the 'Global Positioning Systems Co-ordinates' found in section 3 and 5(g) respectively pending the Courts verdict on the case.

The Court assigned to the respondents the freedom of operating the National Integrated Information Management System (NIIMS) through the collection and storage of personal data based on the Registration of Person's Act with some exceptions. These include a non-obligatory character of the

¹²⁸ Authority of courts to uphold and enforce the Bill of Rights.

¹²⁹ An important principle vital to the court is the respect of the Principle of the Separation of powers.

¹³⁰ Ex: Applicant must demonstrate an arguable prima facie with a likelihood of success; Court should decide whether a grant or denial of conservatory relief would enhance constitutional values of a specific right or freedom in the Bill of rights.

¹³¹ The Computer misuse and Cyber Crimes Act (2018) had been suspended pursuant to a pending case resulting in the lack of a specific provision on the collection, storage and protection of collected data.

¹³² The term 'Public Interest' was defined by the Indian Supreme Court in the case of ' Dattraj Nathuji Thaware v State of Maharashtra, Indian & Others [2004] INSC 755 S.C 755 of 2004' as that which that in which a class of community have a pecuniary interest, or some interest by which their legal rights or liabilities are affected."

¹³³ 'It provides the most reliable personal identification. It is intrinsically digital, and does not change during a person's life or after his/her death.' - DNA biometrics By Masaki Hashiyada.

programme, allowing individuals to freely choose to give out the personal data or not. In circumstances where data is to be given, this should be done without deadlines and time restrictions. Additionally, that the collection of this information will not be set as a mandatory condition prior to accessing any government or public services and facilities; then lastly it prohibits the respondents from sharing data collected by the NIIMS with national or international government and non-governmental bodies, entities or persons.

B) India

4.2.1 Indian legal System

Similar to Kenya, the Indian legal system is based on the English common law system. According to its constitution¹³⁴, it is a federal union made up of 28 states, 6 unions and one national capital territory. The union and states have separate executive and legislative branches although the Union's laws are superior to that of the states. India has a bicameral parliament composed of the upper house Council of States (Rajya Sabha) and the House of People (Lok Sabha). The judiciary is an independent branch of government with the supreme court as its highest form of appellate court.¹³⁵ This is followed by the high courts and the subordinate courts on the district, municipal and local levels.

In 2004 Jayna Kothari, an Indian advocate wrote a commentary on 'Social rights and the Indian Constitution'¹³⁶ portraying that human rights is divided into two parts in the constitution : the 'Fundamental rights' (Part III) include civil and political rights such as the right to life, right to equality, the right to expression, freedom of religion, freedom of movement ; whereas Part IV comprises the Directive Principles of State policy(DPSPs) i.e. the social, economic and cultural rights such as the right to education, the right to health and housing etc. The fundamental rights, recognised internationally, are seen as justiciable by the constitution. The Directive Principles on the other hand, particularly due to their budgetary demands are not justiciable rights, meaning that

¹³⁴ <http://legislative.gov.in/sites/default/files/COI-updated.pdf>

¹³⁵ Mendelsohn, Oliver. "The pathology of the Indian legal system." *Modern Asian Studies* 15.4 (1981): 823-863.

¹³⁶ Kothari, Jayna. "Social rights and the Indian constitution." *Law, Social Justice & Global Development Journal* 2 (2004).

their non-compliance cannot be taken as a claim for enforcement against the State. This is backed by Article 37 of the Indian constitution, which states: ‘The provisions contained in this part shall not be enforceable by any court, but the principles therein laid down are nevertheless fundamental in the governance of the country and it shall be the duty of the state to apply these principles in making laws.’

This emphasizes on the value of these rights in the Indian judicial system and lay a foundation for examining our Indian case. The implementation of the rather complex and unprecedented structure of the Aadhar project raised interest and debate in civil society, gaining the attention and intervention of the Supreme Court. Subsequently, the Indian case is an essential blueprint for identifying the pitfalls and the necessary safeguards associated with the collection and use of biometric data.

4.2.2 The Indian Case Study: Justice K.S.Puttaswamy (Retd) vs Union Of India on 26 September, 2018.

- **Background and facts**

Although India is known for advancement in technology, its judicial scenery has seen in recent times some challenges birthing rapidly by these new technologies. This was the case with the Aadhaar project, a one-to-many identification system initiated officially from 2009 in India by the then Prime Minister Manmohan Singh and then Congress President Sonia Gandhi.

The project was in fact, a materialization of Rajiv Gandhi’s vision of inclusive growth in the country. In detail, citizens were assigned Aadhaar numbers, a twelve-digit code, issued by the Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI), a statutory authority established in 2009 under the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology. The Aadhaar number is generated based on demographic data which includes name, date of birth, gender, address; and biometric data (fingerprints, facial recognition etc) at ‘enrolment centres’ which are both private and public entities.

The idea of building such a project was conceptualized in 2006 with the aim of providing a simplified, valid and efficient model of identification that would provide unique identities to citizens throughout India. More concretely, the unification of the National Population Register (NPR), (a database of the register general that contained a record of all Indian residents), together

with the 'Unique Identification for Below Poverty Line (BPL) families' project led to the creation of the Aadhaar system.¹³⁷ Aside the quest to find identity for its huge population, this was influenced by the issue of effective allocation of benefits, incentives, public services and access to resources to the needy and those that cannot afford a good standard of living.

The Aadhaar's very wide scope was intended to curb difficulties linked to the duplication of identity (theft) and benefits leakages undermining access to state supply and support; the absence of recognized legal identities and other related documents which make it difficult for the individual to access services such as school enrolments and simple tasks like the of opening of bank accounts, thus, accommodating the lack of transparency in the management of cash flows. This would also allow individuals to steer clear of the use of unsecure documents.

In 2012, the Aadhaar project showed the first signs of becoming obligatory. In Mysore, three oil companies had LPG refills connected to the ID generated by this system for a pilot project. Shortly after, in 2013, banks began requesting for the same identification as a requisite to access their services. Additionally, in 2014, the prime minister of India Narendra Modi considered reviewing the progress of the Aadhaar system, expanding its competencies. In 2016, the possibility of using it as a channel to register new-borns to health departments through the Aadhaar ID was also considered aiming to assist states in delivering immunization, health benefits and education to infants before they turned five.¹³⁸

The Aadhaar, in its methodology, deposits all data into a central database called the Central Identities Repository, with the supervision of the UIDAI, after enrolment and the issuing of the number. To access any type of benefit or subsidiaries from the government, particularly from the Consolidated fund of India, the citizen had to first run an identity authentication at the 'Requesting Entities' department to make sure biometric data and other information concerning individual matched with initial data stored in the UIDAI centralized repository. The system, through what we described earlier as the one-to-many procedure, confirms the uniqueness of the identity to be

¹³⁷ Ghangare, Ajay, and Anup Ranade. "Aadhar Card–Perspectives on Privacy." *Journal of International Pharmaceutical Research* (2018)

¹³⁸ To read more: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/technology/modi-government-to-give-aadhaar-to-newborns/articleshow/52442912.cms>

processed with other administrative procedures. Currently, India's repository stores the sensitive data of 1.2 billion Indian citizens.¹³⁹

Though the Aadhaar system was initiated for a good cause, it experienced the emergence of some pitfalls and problematic issues. The long absence of a tangible legal base that could monitor the efficiency of the Aadhaar system as well as a specific legislation on privacy and data protection, considering the idiosyncrasy and sensitivity related to the biometric data. This need protruded distinctly after the Aadhaar act¹⁴⁰(2016) required, that citizens possess their ID number prior to accessing a continuously expanding range of benefits and services; extending this condition to the private sector (banks, telecommunication companies) rendering it obligatory to give out biometric and demographic data prior to achieving simple tasks like buying a sim card.

These arguments have resulted in the rise of doubts, within civil society and various organizations protecting the citizens' rights, concerning the adequacy and proportionality of the processing of data collected and stored for the provision of the Aadhaar number, and more broadly, the constitutional validity.

The very first petition challenging Aadhaar was filed in November 2012¹⁴¹ by the retired Justice K. S. Puttaswamy through a Writ Petition based on the grounds that it violated the right to privacy protected by Article 21¹⁴² of the Indian Constitution.

In addition to the reasons mentioned previously, issues raised by the petitions include the possibility of the Aadhaar creating a surveillance state and violating the rights to privacy; the constitutionality of the system; the kind of protection accorded to the collection and storage of biometric data.

This petition was contended by the Union of India and the Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI). The stand taken by them is that the right to privacy could not be considered a fundamental right. This was upheld by an eight-Judge Bench that denied that citizens had a fundamental right to privacy in the hearings, this was contended again. The claim became a vital point, because the Supreme Court could not hear the broader constitutional challenge to Aadhaar unless the matter at hand was resolved.

¹³⁹ R. Kalra, R. Verma, C. Nasa, Aadhaar Thumb: one platform to all services, International Journal of Recent Research Aspects, 1 (201hk8) pg.12-14

¹⁴⁰ Aadhaar (Targeted delivery of financial and other subsidies, benefits and services) Act, 25 marzo 2016.

¹⁴¹ Writ petition no. 494 of 2012

¹⁴² Protection of life and personal liberty No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law.

At this point of the case, various petitions were made resulting in interim orders being issued ever so often concerning the operations of the Aadhaar pending the hearing of the court on its constitutional validity. Firstly, similar to the National Integrated Identity Management System (NIIMS) case, the court ordered that the mandatory aspect of the registration issued by some authorities be suspended until further notice. Other orders were passed concerning the limited use of the information collected within the scope of the Aadhaar project; the suspension of the registration as a condition for accessing benefits; the constitutional validity of linking bank accounts and mobile phones with Aadhaar IDs¹⁴³

Meanwhile, in March 2016, the government introduced the controversial Aadhaar bill as a money bill in Parliament. The government was accused by opposition parties of using the money bill as a tool to circumvent the Rajya Sabha, where the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) did not hold a majority. The bill, however, was passed in the Lok Sabha and although the Congress, which retained a majority in the Rajya Sabha, returned the bill with five amendments, they were rejected by the BJP and the bill was considered to have been passed. The bill was contested through the filing of a second writ petition by the retired Justice K. S. Puttaswamy in the same year, leading to a consolidation of the writ petitions. Shortly after, in May 2017, the former Union Minister and Congress leader Jairam Ramesh also challenged the Centre's decision of the Aadhaar bill as a money bill at the supreme Court. That same year, a nine-judge bench of the Honourable Supreme Court made an important ruling¹⁴⁴: that the right to privacy is a Fundamental Right. A verdict traceable to part III of the Constitution of India that lays out provisions affirming the fundamental rights of citizens; especially article 21 that reads: "No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law." The court added that any invasion of privacy by the state or any non-state actors must satisfy three elements, the legitimate aim of the action or law, proportionality and legality. This turned the course of events thereafter. On January 17th the following year, a five-judge bench of the Supreme Court began hearing the Aadhaar case.

¹⁴³ Justice K.S.Puttaswamy (Retd) vs Union Of India on 26 September, 2018. (par 17-21)

¹⁴⁴ a panel chaired by the Chief Justice, acknowledged the importance of the question submitted to the Supreme Court (in the case concerning the legitimacy of the Aadhaar identification system, ed.) And of the fact that the decisions M PSharma and Kharak Singh had been issued respectively by a panel of eight and six judges, ordered that the matter be examined by a judging body composed of nine judges. Also see); R. Singh, Human dignity and right to privacy: the Puttaswamy Judgement, in India Constitutional Law Review Blog, 6 maggio 2018. <http://iclrq.in/blog-posts/human-dignity-and-right-to-privacy-the-puttaswamy-judgment/>

The lawyers¹⁴⁵ representing the petitioners argued possible risks that could affect individual rights and liberties due to the strict implementation of the Aadhaar, and how they had to satisfy the laws laid out by the constitution. It described the restrictions imposed by the government on the exercise of the right to privacy as unreasonable and somewhat unfair. Compelling people to disclose their religion is a violation of Art 25 of the Constitution related to the freedom of conscience and free profession, practice and propagation of religion.

Other issues raised were the possible enabling of an intrusive state that would transform into a surveillance state through the collection of personal information from citizens and the extension of the Aadhaar platform to government and private bodies (section 57 of the Aadhaar Act); the authority installed on the UIDAI to ‘omit permanently or deactivate temporarily’ the Aadhaar ID anytime, depriving the individual from accessing benefits for which the number is a requisite; the mandatory possession of the ID number prior to applying for benefits and non-benefit schemes would deprive them of their right to choice or the ‘decisional autonomy’ of the individual, a violation of the right to life, a fundamental right of the constitution. In this regard, Shyam Divan, one of the four lawyers also challenged the section 7 of the Aadhaar Act¹⁴⁶ and emphasized that the constitution requires the state to provide benefits, subsidies and services to its citizens.

The petitioners further requested that the entire Aadhaar Act passed in 2016 be struck down since procedures engaged did not fulfil the criteria for a money bill.

In summary, the claims reiterated, that the Aadhaar Act, contrary to its real purpose, violated the balance between the citizens and the state, also due to the absence of a ‘compelling state interest’ which would authorize the collection of information according to Article 14. The failure to account for subsidies, services and benefits and give hypothetical figures for savings is further considered a concrete reason why citizens should not be forced to get an Aadhaar card.

The respondents rebutted the arguments brought forth by the petitioners assuring the court that individuals eligible for any such benefits were not deprived of it even in cases where there was a non-matching data during authentication. In demonstrating that information collected was non-invasive and non-intrusive, regarding the risk of state surveillance, they averred that the structure of the system received minimum information such as the name, date of birth, address, gender, mobile

¹⁴⁵ Shyam Divan, Kapil Sibal, Arvind Datar, P Chidambaram

¹⁴⁶ Section 7 covers the schemes eligible beneficiaries- targeted delivery of financial and other subsidiaries, benefits and services.

number and email address (the last two being optional). To protect individuals from any form of discrimination, following the provisions of section 2(k) that aims at excluding sensitive data such as ethnicity, caste, tribe, religion etc.; the demographic information requested is narrow and concise. The biometric data used, in their opinion, referred majorly to the iris scan and fingerprints which formed the core biometric data used by various identification systems in the world.

In proving the existence of data protection and informational privacy provisions, they referred to the draft of the Personal Data Protection Bill (2018), mentioned in the preceding chapter, released to address the processing of personal data. This draft aimed to create a trust- based relationship between the ‘fiduciary’, i.e the entity that possesses the data and the ‘principal’ i.e the data subject. As stated beforehand, the bill incorporated data protection principles from the EUGDPR such as purpose limitation, storage limitation, data processing, data quality and accountability. It calls out the rights and obligations of both the fiduciary and the data subject including the right to access and correction, right to data portability, the right to prevent or restrict disclosure of personal data by fiduciary etc. An additional element highlighted in this draft is the importance of giving individual consent before processing their personal data.

The respondents further argued reasons why the Aadhaar card should remain mandatory: they acknowledged the Aadhaar system would restructure the role of the state in society, increasing the quality of services given to the public. In their perspective, making the registration to the Aadhaar system voluntary would eventually stake a stall on majority of the population since they would not be able to access most social schemes.

Through the direct cash system introduced by the Aadhaar scheme, to substitute the delivery of food, water, electricity and the like; timely payments are guaranteed cutting off inefficiencies, transaction costs, middlemen and leakages. This increases the government’s focus and enables it to provide directly to individuals and groups eligible for assistance or attention. It streamlines the system, easing the identification of duplications, fraud activities and tax invaders in the country. Veritably, the Aadhaar ID was requested when applying for the permanent account number applications (PAN) and filing income taxes.

In brief, the respondents affirmed the Aadhaar to be an effective tool of governance that would impact positively the development of India as a whole in terms of productivity, equality, transparency and accountability.

Court analysis and disposition.

Prior to reaching its final decision, the Honourable Supreme Court analysed the many facets dealt with in this case, scrutinizing the alleged dangers of the Aadhaar system. It tackled mainly doubts raised on the uniqueness of the Aadhaar system; privacy, data protection and surveillance; data management, proportionality amongst others.

Picking up its discourse from clarifying the doubt tied to violations against the right to privacy, the Court deems the Aadhaar constitutional due to its minimum invasion in comparison to how efficient it is in 'ensuring good governance in the social welfare state.' As a result, it is of their opinion that the Aadhaar system 'struck a fair balance between the right to privacy of the individual and the right to life of the same individual as beneficiary.'¹⁴⁷

On September 26th, 2018, the Hon'ble Supreme Court passed a very detailed judgement of a little more than a thousand pages. In brief, it upheld the constitutional validity of the Aadhaar card but struck down certain provisions of the Aadhaar Act. Although, the court admonished the Parliament and authorities of the need for a suitable regulatory system on the subject of privacy and data protection, the Court held that even considering the margin of error and alleged negative effects caused by use of biometric data, particularly the one-to-many identification procedure, was still not a sufficient argument to regard the entire system as unconstitutional. In their own words they state that 'the remedy is to plug the loopholes rather than axe a project, aimed at the welfare of a large section of the society.'¹⁴⁸

In light of this, the system was therefore considered excessively damaging to privacy where it establishes that biometric data are provided for purposes that do not aim to guarantee human dignity, in the form of access to essential subsidies and services. The Court ordered that the mandatory nature of the Aadhaar identification system be prohibited. This applied also to all minors, rendering illegitimate the compulsory possession of the Aadhaar number. Through this modification, banks, telephone operators and some institutions would no longer request for Aadhaar code as an exclusive condition for opening current accounts, purchasing of sim cards, school enrolments and other services.

¹⁴⁷ Par. 309-313, Justice Puttaswamy v. Union of India.

¹⁴⁸ Par. 219, Justice Puttaswamy v. Union of India

Additionally, the judgment pronounced other major changes requiring normative changes: in relation to section 2(d) of the Aadhaar Act, the court ruled that authentication record should not include metadata¹⁴⁹. The time of retention of personal data records was scaled down from 7 years to six months. In the same way, the judges imposed on the legislator a modification of Section 33¹⁵⁰, (such as including reviews done by the oversight committee, consisting of the Cabinet Secretary and the Secretaries to the Government of India in the Department of Legal Affairs and the Department of Electronics and Information Technology, before it takes effect), to protect more extensively, the individual.

Sections 47 (attributed to the cognizance of offences) and 57(the use of Aadhaar data by any “corporate body or person” to establish the identity of an individual) are also struck down by the Court. By the Court’s verdict, ‘no court is allowed to take cognizance of any offence punishable under this Act, except on a complaint made by the authority of office or person authorised by it. The Section also disallows courts below that of a Chief Metropolitan Magistrate or a Chief Judicial Magistrate to trial any offence punishable under this Act.’ Secondly, Section 57 reads:

“Nothing contained in this Act shall prevent the use of Aadhaar number for establishing the identity of an individual for any purpose, whether by the State or anybody corporate or person, pursuant to any law, for the time being in force, or any contract to this effect: Provided that the use of Aadhaar number under this section shall be subject to the procedure and obligations under section 8 and Chapter VI.’

This provision, as mentioned previously, authorized private companies like Paytm¹⁵¹ and Airtel Payments Bank to sought Aadhaar details from customers and was found unconstitutional by the Court.

In essence, the Supreme court of India, although in favour of development and innovation in the country (particularly advanced technology, capable of incrementing the efficiency of the intervention of the State in promoting fundamental rights and social rights), questions its increasingly invasive attributes in terms of privacy and how personal information is processed. This

¹⁴⁹ Data that provides information about another data. In this case it refers to all the information that encompass the results of the authentication operations requested by the citizen.

¹⁵⁰ Section 33 of the Aadhaar Act refers to disclosure of information in certain cases. The Supreme Court has read down Section 33(1) while striking down 33(2). Section 33(1) allows disclosure of information, including identity and authentication records, if ordered by a court not inferior to that of District Judge. Section 33 (2) allows identity and authentication data to be disclosed in the interest of national security on direction of an officer not below the rank of Joint Secretary to the Government of India.

¹⁵¹ Associated with digital banking

has resulted in unprecedented challenges to legislators and judges and the law field at large, as seen on the international platform. Acknowledging the continuous growth of the tech field, the court urges, that the use of identification, based on such sensitive data must be handled with caution and attention, keeping in mind the interest of national security yet finding a balance with the rights of the individual through the principle of proportionality. In his *dissenting opinion*¹⁵², Justice D. Chandrachud, referred to the words of Professor Upendra Baxi¹⁵³ of the need for a correct balance between ‘*bread and freedom*’ and ‘*between human rights and rights to be human.*’

Additionally, the verdict ordered a ‘backward’ intervention: that appropriate amendments be made to the Aadhaar Act 2016, correcting the already existing system to meet the new standards. It urges the legislative bodies to work towards building adequate laws to protect the right to privacy and the protection of data. In achieving all this, the “policy before technology”¹⁵⁴ principle is salient and should be applied before the erection of such advanced systems. Evidently, India failed to implement principle in developing the Aadhaar system, inserting ad hoc regulatory frameworks only after the emergence of legal problems and numerous appeals.

4.3 – Comparative analysis on judgements.

“Governments are coming up with these schemes, saying it’s mainly to improve welfare services and better security, but in fact they are not limiting the purposes for which the data can be used or adopting essential safeguards, which results in dramatic overreach,” P. Alston says. “And once you start doing this in countries that don’t have a very strong rule of law tradition, you’re really opening it up to all sorts of deep corruption and oppression.”¹⁵⁵

The National Integrated Information Management System (NIIMS) and the Aadhaar system were both initiated by the government to better their method of intervention in Kenya and India respectively. In their opinion, creating a centralized database or repository to house the personal information and biometric data of the citizens and residents would ease the process of identifying

¹⁵² Dissenting Opinion, Giudice D. Chandrachud, Justice Puttaswamy v. Union of India, sentenza del 26 settembre 2018 (D.N. 35071/2012), Corte Suprema indiana, par. 179.

¹⁵³ Par. 103, Dissenting Opinion, Giudice Chandrachud, Justice Puttaswamy v. Union of India.

¹⁵⁴ An expression used by P. Dixon in A failure to “Do no harm” –India’s Aadhaar biometric ID program and its inability to protect privacy in relation to measures in Europe and the U.S., op. cit., 9

¹⁵⁵ Alston, Philip. "Report of the Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights." (2015) par

individuals and/or families eligible for benefits, subsidies and other forms of assistance, diminish fraudulent activities related to these schemes, increase accountability and transparency.

In both cases, we see a parallel turn of events that lead to Supreme Court judgements. The main claims made towards the NIIMS were the legally inappropriate or unconstitutional method through which it was passed, the exemption of public participation and consent, the direct exclusion of some minorities, the lack of reliable safeguards that protect the fundamental individual rights, and the fact that it was made obligatory; whereas the main allegations made towards the Aadhaar included the violation of the individual's right to privacy and the right to life, inadequate security guarding these rights that could lead to possible establishment of a surveillance state considering the level of intrusiveness into the citizens' life, the suspicious means through which the Aadhaar Bill was passed.

These downsides were fuelled mainly by a lack of detailed, structured and inclusive legal provisions that addressed beforehand, the method of data collection and processing not to mention limitations to what these systems are entitled to do. Moreover, Kenya instituted the NIIMS by submitting amendments to the registration of persons Act passed through an omnibus Act in the Kenyan Gazette whereas the Aadhaar Act was passed circa four years after it was launched. This exhibits the ill-considered approach taken by both countries in implementing these identification systems and safeguarding the individual rights.

In both cases the courts judged in favour of the identification systems, leaving them in operation. A step, that validates the importance of the role technology plays in our world, introducing innovation in governance and policy making. However, the suspension and elimination of biased aspects of the systems in both verdicts throw light on the existing pitfalls of such schemes.

The meteoric rise and current growth in the tech field has transformed it into what is considered a monopoly¹⁵⁶ on its own, capable of creating new data caches in areas such as finance and healthcare, with undertakings that allow them to collaborate with and mine data from banks, hospitals, and insurance companies. This perception is an admissible reason why the legal field should be called out to enact legislations that complement the digital welfare state's demands. Both courts focus on creating balance between efficient structures and the protection of fundamental human rights. In the Aadhaar case, the Indian Supreme Court focuses on the proportionality test with

¹⁵⁶ See more on the growth of tech companies in the world <https://www.ft.com/content/f7b13372-3797-11ea-a6d3-9a26f8c3c3ba4>

meticulous precision, examining the individual provisions of the Aadhaar Act challenged by the applicants, with a reconstruction that also looks beyond national borders. In fact, attention is paid to a current analysis of new technologies, the impact of big data and their attributes made up of potentials and threats¹⁵⁷, as well as the most relevant foreign judgements on the subject, from referencing the rulings of the American Supreme Court to that of the Court of Justice of the European Union and the European Court of Human Rights¹⁵⁸. (The role of comparison is highlighted in the Indian judgement representing an underlying element in both the actual ruling and the previous ruling on the right to confidentiality/privacy). Regarding this balance, they observe overt obstacles that seem to emerge as competing interests within the notion of ‘public interest’: functional systems that operate efficiently towards the needs of the individual (respecting the right to live a dignified life) vs the protection of the individual’s privacy.

Although, in comparison to the Aadhaar case, the NIIMS case is marginally behind since the judgement made was in relation to the issuing of conservatory orders pending the determination of the consolidated petitions; it is apparent that in both cases the functioning and efficiency of the government and its public administration is held in high esteem. This could be interpreted as the adoption of the ‘just, fair and reasonable’¹⁵⁹ standard instead of the ‘strict scrutiny’ standard in judging these cases respecting the principle of the separation of powers. De facto, the Kenyan court refused to suspend or in the petitioner’s own terms ‘prohibit the respondents and their agents from implementing sections 3,5(g) & 9 of the registration of persons’ Act (that included the launch of NIIMS). They chose not to issue the conservatory orders on the terms prayed but laid out other orders like the suspension of specific types of biometric data (ex: Digital DNA). Similarly, the Indian court upheld the validity of the Aadhaar card but eliminated other provisions they found incoherent to the constitution.

It is important to note that Kenya and India, as most digital welfare states, have had minimum experience with technology in governance, rendering both cases unprecedented in these countries. Nonetheless, the main point of reference and guide for both circumstances has been the constitution

¹⁵⁷ Par. 159-162, Justice Puttaswamy v. Union of India

¹⁵⁸ Par. 84, Justice Puttaswamy v. Union of India: “In this hue, it can also be remarked that comparative law has played a very significant role in shaping the aforesaid judgment on privacy in Indian context, notwithstanding the fact that such comparative law has only a persuasive value.”

¹⁵⁹ See highlights of the Aadhaar case <https://www.sflc.in/key-highlights-aadhaar-judgment>

and its fundamental rights, assigning to the legislative bodies a responsibility to rise to the still emerging technologically driven innovations world-wide.

Conclusion

The welfare state has come a long way in developing a modern state that encompasses a blend of the liberal, conservative and social-democratic systems, acknowledging the importance of the fundamental rights of its citizens. To render its governance more efficient, credible and reliable, accelerating processing speeds, technological innovations particularly AI, have been adopted overtime through various software and automated systems.¹⁶⁰ These automated tools are used in several fields and different stages within the welfare context including health, identification, welfare benefit calculation and payments, eligibility assessments, and even justice.

In this study, we have unearthed the nature of advanced technology (AI) and its advantages as well as disadvantages on the welfare state; simultaneously weighing our legal frameworks and digging into their scope in relation to this very subject. As discussed, the very dynamic nature of technology has raised some doubts in our society. The tech field has experienced a rapid advancement, enough to be considered a monopoly on its own with a necessity to thrive in our modern world. According to Forbes, technology is currently one of the world's largest industries with investment increasing by 3.1 billion pounds in 2019 alone, giving them 'unprecedented power over the marketplaces they facilitate' and control to set rules under which other businesses should operate. These companies additionally take responsibility for democratising the access to AI and enabling advancements in the field; but the extent of this is to their will.¹⁶¹

Aside these general concerns, the welfare state faces other invisible yet weighty problems from the operation of automated systems: the risk of generating surveillance systems, ; the perils of algorithmic decision-making based on systematic biases, the difficulty of appealing against computer-generated determinations or even pleading for justifying circumstances to an algorithm. The identification systems, though developed to promote the wellbeing of citizens and reduce inequalities¹⁶², have also paradoxically generated data breaches, intrusive behaviour and privacy infringements, that have led to the exclusion of the vulnerable; an abuse of the purpose for which they were designed. As portrayed in both the Kenyan and Indian cases, the existing deficit in the

¹⁶⁰ Offe, Claus. "II. Democracy against the welfare state? Structural foundations of neoconservative political opportunities." *Political theory* 15.4 (1987): 501-537.

¹⁶¹ Kasia Borowska, *The Monopoly On Technology And How To Defeat It*. Retrieved at <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kasiaborowska/2020/12/15/the-monopoly-on-technology-and-how-to-defeat-it/?sh=61ae844621af>. Accessed Dec 15 2020

¹⁶² Also related to goals 1,2,3,4 address poverty, hunger, good health and wellbeing respectively; whereas goal 10 tackles the reduction of inequalities.

legal structures on automation, data protection and their enforcement even in various countries further aggravates the state of our systems which may lead to the previously mentioned ‘welfare dystopia’ characterized by an unbalance between strategies implemented by the government and the safeguarding of fundamental rights.

The welfare state’s task in rebuilding this equilibrium, is linked to the United Nations 2030 sustainable development goals. Goal 9 addresses the industry, innovation and infrastructure. It is important for welfare states to adapt to the technological innovations whilst building resilient infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization. Constructing a healthy, sustainable, safe and inclusive society should be the target of policy makers and welfare state authorities (goal 11), ascertaining that communities and citizens are not affected negatively by such ‘development.’ More Precisely, peace, justice and strong institutions should be ensured by the welfare state to provide justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels (goal 16).

Timnit Gebru, a renowned computer scientist and AI ethicist, in the case of ‘Artificial intelligence and marginalizing communities’ stated, that the most important questions to ask are if it is imperative for such tools to be used’ and secondly, ‘if such tools are robust enough to be used for such high-state scenarios.’¹⁶³ As mentioned hitherto, in machine learning, the systematic errors created by these tools through automation biases i.e the absence of critical thinking, could give wrong outcomes and ultimately be harmful to some individuals and our societies at large.¹⁶⁴ Subsequently, this renders the automated systems incapable of making correct decisions, propagating biases, discriminations and infringements, altering the sustainable development in communities.

‘Many of the programmes used to promote the digital welfare state have been designed by the very same companies that are so deeply resistant to abiding by human rights standards. Moreover, those companies and their affiliates are increasingly relied upon to design and implement key parts of the welfare programmes themselves. It is evidence that the starting point for efforts to ensure human rights-compatible digital welfare state outcomes is to ensure, through governmental regulation, that

¹⁶³ ‘Artificial Intelligence and marginalizing communities.’ Timnit discusses the possible errors automated systems could generate and their effects on some groups in society.

¹⁶⁴ For alternative example of such tools see the immigration and customs Enforcement- ICE’s Extreme Vetting initiatives, aimed to partnership with tech companies to analyse the social network activities of some individuals in order to determine whether they are in the position to commit a certain crime or not. Such a system is most likely to fault due to systematic errors that only humans would pick up.

technology companies are legally required to respect applicable international human rights standards.’¹⁶⁵

Technological innovations should be engrafted more intentionally into the welfare state based on specified or concrete legal provisions ensuring legality and transparency, promoting digital equality, protecting economic, social, civil and political rights in the digital welfare state. This brings us to the concept of a ‘sustainable digital welfare state’ in which governments enact adequate normative provisions, fiscal policies and incentives, and are committed to constructing a welfare system solid enough to ensure a decent standard of living.

In employing Gebru’s questions to our case, we must answer as to if we deem the use of automated tools indispensable in our sustainable digital welfare state. Secondly, if these tools are robust enough to shoulder very sensitive and vital decision- making exercises and lastly if our legal systems are equipped to foster said innovative schemes.

Still in conjunction with our Kenyan and Indian case studies, it is evident that welfare states are spearheading innovative actions or initiatives, as was respected by both supreme courts and upheld constitutional. Yet still, taking into account the various pitfalls of Artificial Intelligence and automated systems, assigning to them particular tasks such as storing huge databases consisting of sensitive data and handling automated decision-making may appear too straining for such systems, further obstructing the progress of welfare systems. This highlights the lack of structured legal frameworks that elaborate standards for which automated systems should be built as well as appropriate limitations in order to safeguard measures protecting citizens; confirming the notion that digital capabilities utilized by the digital welfare state reflect the existing policies and normative frameworks.

Gebru suggests that datasheets consisting of standardized processes be created to document datasheets just like what happens the electronic industry, where datasheets are released with each component explaining the ‘operating characteristics, test results, recommended uses and other information.’¹⁶⁶ In addition, this should be ‘accompanied by its motivation, collection process, recommended uses etc. in order to facilitate communication between dataset creators and users and encourage the machine learning community to prioritize transparency and accountability.

¹⁶⁵ Report of the Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights
<https://undocs.org/A/74/493> Par 75

¹⁶⁶ Gebru, Timnit, et al. "Datasheets for datasets." arXiv preprint arXiv:1803.09010 (2018).

Another issue to be tackled is the diversity crisis present in the AI industry especially in relation to gender and race.¹⁶⁷ The continuous complacency with the homogeneity of developers in general AI related developing and welfare tasks in particular, causes the digital welfare state to reflect certain perspectives and life experiences based on personal values and perceptions. It is salient that diversity is made a requirement, and the group of people creating these systems resemble the group of users to avoid any form of biases and discriminations.

In ‘New Laws of Robotics: Defending Human Expertise in the Age of AI’¹⁶⁸, Frank Pasquale discusses the humane vision of robotics and artificial intelligence, how technology is to promote the wellbeing of people. Technology should not be a mere tool that imitates or substitutes them; rather, it must work with humans for humans, promoting social cooperation and improving tasks.

We would all agree that the law is the only element capable of promoting equality and fundamental rights. As an instrument of every sustainable digital welfare state, it must provide balanced guidelines comprising specific standards, laws and requisites related to technological innovations and automated systems. In invoking social protection, roles pertaining to the private sectors involved in proposing, developing and operating digital technologies should be clearly defined, also for future purposes. The digital welfare revolution should sustain the wellbeing of individuals and provide a higher standard of living with systems devised to care for the vulnerable, unemployed, marginalized and the less privileged. Anything outside this should be questioned by the Law.

¹⁶⁷ Stats show that women make up 15 per cent of artificial intelligence research staff at Facebook and 10 per cent at Google; only 2.5 per cent of Google’s workforce is black, while Facebook and Microsoft are each at 4 per cent (Sarah West, Meredith Whittaker and Kate Crawford, “Discriminating systems: gender, race and power in AI” (AI Now Institute, 2019))

¹⁶⁸ Pasquale, Frank. *New Laws of Robotics*. Harvard University Press, 2020.

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